

Which transmission condition is the best in optimized Schwarz waveform relaxation for viscoelastic equation: Robin or characteristic?

Fu Li¹ and Yingxiang Xu^{1*}

¹School of Mathematics and Statistics, Northeast Normal University,
5268 Renmin Street, Changchun, 130024, JiLin Province, People's
Republic of China.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): yxxu@nenu.edu.cn;
Contributing authors: lif097@nenu.edu.cn;

Abstract

The viscoelastic equation introduces a viscoelastic damping term in the classical wave equation, thus exhibits properties of parabolic systems accompanied by hyperbolic properties. On the other hand, it is well known that for parabolic systems, when solved using the optimized Schwarz waveform relaxation (OSWR) method, Robin transmission condition is preferred, however characteristic transmission condition is good for hyperbolic system. In this paper, we investigate what transmission condition should be applied according to different strengths of damping. The results show that, in the OSWR algorithm, for weak damping the characteristic transmission condition is preferred, while for strong damping one should use Robin instead, as anticipated. It is also observed that the convergence depends on the relationship between the temporal and spatial mesh sizes applied, which shows overlap may not accelerate the convergence. In addition, we find numerically that a mix of both transmission conditions can only improve the convergence for strong damping, and it remains to be an interesting problem to look for transmission conditions that are more robust in the damping strength.

Keywords: Domain decomposition, Optimized Schwarz waveform relaxation, Viscoelastic equation, Transmission condition

MSC Classification: 65M55 , 65Y05

1 Introduction

We focus on the optimized Schwarz waveform relaxation (OSWR) method for the one-dimensional viscoelastic equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 \partial_{tt}u(x, t) - \varepsilon\partial_{txx}u(x, t) - \gamma\partial_{xx}u(x, t) &= f(x, t), \quad (x, t) \in \Omega \times J, \\
 u(x, t) &= \phi(x, t), \quad (x, t) \in \partial\Omega \times J, \\
 u(x, 0) &= \psi_1(x), \quad x \in \Omega, \\
 \partial_t u(x, 0) &= \psi_2(x), \quad x \in \Omega,
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where Ω is the space domain, $J = (0, T]$ is the time interval, $\varepsilon > 0$ is the viscoelastic damping coefficient and $\sqrt{\gamma}$ is the wave velocity with $\gamma > 0$. The source function $f \in L^2(0, T; L^2(\Omega))$, the boundary function $\phi(x, t) \in C^2(0, T; C^2(\partial\Omega))$ and the initial functions $\psi_1(x) \in H_0^1(\Omega)$ and $\psi_2(x) \in L^2(\Omega)$ are given [13]. Compared to the classical wave equation, the viscoelastic equation uses a damping term $-\varepsilon\partial_{txx}u$ to provide a more accurate model in many applications, for example, the propagation of vibration waves through viscoelastic media [36]. We refer the reader to [48] for more applications in science and engineering. Recently, Gander et al. [23] numerically validated that the viscoelastic damping $-\varepsilon\partial_{txx}u$ works much better than the first order damping term $-\partial_t u$ (which results in the telegrapher's equation) for modeling the vibration of an elastic string.

The well-posedness of the viscoelastic equation has been studied extensively [2, 42, 44]. Very recently, there has been significant research focused on the decay properties and the asymptotic behavior of solutions [3, 10, 30]. However, analytical solutions for many practical PDEs are often elusive, due to complex data (e.g., intricate initial or boundary conditions, sophisticated sources, discontinuous coefficients) and complex domain geometries. Therefore, it is essential to study the numerical methods for solving the viscoelastic equation. In fact, all prevalent techniques for spatial discretization can be applied to the viscoelastic equation (1), see [46] for the finite element methods, [4] for the mixed finite element methods, [32] for the finite difference methods, [35] for the generalized finite difference methods (also known as finite volume element methods), [45] for the discontinuous Galerkin methods, and [47] for the weak Galerkin finite element methods, etc. Recently, meshless methods have also gained attention in solving the viscoelastic equation (1), as demonstrated in [40, 41].

However, most numerical methods for solving equation (1) are based on time stepping. For example, the reader can refer to [38, 50] for a Crank-Nicolson scheme, where an extrapolation approach and a proper orthogonal decomposition technique are used to reduce the degree of freedom. In fact, there is not much experience in parallel computation for solving the viscoelastic equation. Adey and Brebbia [1] proposed long ago to solve the viscoelastic equation in parallel in the Laplace transformed plane by the finite element method, and then a least square collocation method is applied to construct the whole solution in the time domain. And the authors [34] studied a diagonalization-based parallel-in-time algorithm for Crank-Nicolson's discretization of the viscoelastic equation, and through rigorous analysis, found that the spectral radius of the iteration matrix is uniformly bounded by $v/(1-v)$, where $v \in (0, \frac{1}{2})$ is a free parameter, independent of the model parameters and the discretization parameters.

However, except for the above-mentioned works, we do not find any published articles concerning the parallel computing of viscoelastic equations. To speedup the computation, we turn our attention to the waveform relaxation method based on domain decomposition, which is developed for evolution equations [26, 22, 27].

The domain decomposition method originated from Schwarz's seminal work [43] in 1870, and was developed in 1990 by Lions [37] as a parallel solver, which finally led to the optimized Schwarz algorithms, cf.[20, 14] and references cited therein. Nowadays the optimized Schwarz algorithm has received extensive attention from many scholars and has been successfully used in many stationary engineering models, such as [20, 11, 52]. The waveform relaxation algorithm was invented to solve the extremely large system of evolution differential equations that arise in circuit simulations [33]. Therefore, the waveform relaxation method has been applied to the solution of many different types of problems, for example, the fractional differential equation [31], the singular perturbation problem [53], etc.

The Schwarz waveform relaxation (SWR) algorithm was proposed for space-time problems [26, 22], and independently in [27], at the continuous level. The spatial domain is decomposed into subdomains, and time-dependent problems are solved iteratively on subdomains, exchanging information at the interfaces between subdomains. This approach [17] permits a different numerical treatment in both space and time of the subdomain problems, and subdomain information is exchanged less often. Similar to the Schwarz algorithm, the SWR method shows fast convergence when using optimized transmission conditions, as first shown in [18], and then treated in detail in [7, 17, 39, 6, 49, 9] for the diffusive problems, [16, 19] for the wave equation, see also the circuit problems in [15, 21], the heterogeneous problems in [28, 29], and the models with discontinuous coefficients [8].

In this paper, we study the OSWR algorithm for solving the viscoelastic equation (1), and three different transmission conditions are under consideration, aiming at analyzing the effects of the damping strength on the algorithm's performance. We designed Robin transmission condition for addressing relatively strong damping strength, and a characteristic condition for relatively weak damping. Targeting on making the transmission condition more robust in the damping strength ε , we designed a hybrid transmission condition by mixing the above two. These three transmission conditions are rigorously optimized in an asymptotic sense, using the idea applied in [25, 24]. We consider both cases with and without overlap and derive closed-form solutions for the optimized parameters in an asymptotic sense as well as the estimates of the corresponding convergence factors. Interesting findings include, first, the asymptotic behavior of the OSWR algorithm depends not only on the temporal mesh size τ , but also on δ , when τ is related to the spatial mesh size h by $\tau \sim h^\delta$; second, an overlap does not always accelerate the convergence of the OSWR algorithm; lastly, the mixed transmission condition, as the combination of Robin and characteristic conditions, still encounter problems in dealing with problems with weak damp.

This paper is organized as follows. In Sect. 2, we present the OSWR algorithm for the viscoelastic equation (1). To achieve fast convergence, we devise three transmission conditions for efficiently transferring information between subdomains. We also derive the convergence factor using Fourier analysis. In Sections 3, 4, and 5 we

analyze the asymptotic convergence results for the Robin, characteristic, and mixed transmission conditions, respectively. By solving the min-max problem for the convergence factor in the Fourier frequency domain in an asymptotic sense, we optimize the transmission parameters involved in the subdomain iterations. In Sect. 6, we illustrate our theoretical results using numerical experiments. We then conclude in Sect. 7.

2 The optimized Schwarz waveform relaxation algorithm

To well illustrate the theoretical analysis, we consider only a one-dimensional problem and assume that the defining domain is an infinite domain $\Omega = \mathbb{R}$ for ease of analysis. We note that the case of finite defining domains and high-dimensional problems can also be analyzed similarly, but requires a more intricate analysis. As established in [51], the discrepancy between the convergence factors of the infinite- and finite-domain analyses is bounded by a term that decays exponentially with the subdomain size. Thus, the infinite-domain analysis yields satisfactory results as long as the subdomains are not too small. Furthermore, we consider only the two-subdomain scenario here for the sake of analytical simplicity, and the analysis can be extended to the case of multiple subdomains. We thus suppose that the defining domain Ω is decomposed as $\overline{\Omega} = \overline{\Omega}_1 \cup \overline{\Omega}_2$ with $\Omega_1 = (-\infty, L)$ and $\Omega_2 = (0, +\infty)$, where L indicates the overlap between subdomains. The classical SWR algorithm for the model problem (1) is given by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \partial_{tt}u_1^n(x, t) - \varepsilon\partial_{ttx}u_1^n(x, t) - \gamma\partial_{xx}u_1^n(x, t) = f(x, t), \quad (x, t) \in \Omega_1 \times (0, T], \\ u_1^n(L, t) = u_2^{n-1}(L, t), \quad t \in (0, T], \\ u_1^n(x, 0) = \psi_1(x), \quad x \in \Omega_1, \\ \partial_t u_1^n(x, 0) = \psi_2(x), \quad x \in \Omega_1, \\ \partial_{tt}u_2^n(x, t) - \varepsilon\partial_{ttx}u_2^n(x, t) - \gamma\partial_{xx}u_2^n(x, t) = f(x, t), \quad (x, t) \in \Omega_2 \times (0, T], \\ u_2^n(0, t) = u_1^{n-1}(0, t), \quad t \in (0, T], \\ u_2^n(x, 0) = \psi_1(x), \quad x \in \Omega_2, \\ \partial_t u_2^n(x, 0) = \psi_2(x), \quad x \in \Omega_2. \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

By linearity, it suffices to consider only the case $f = 0$, which corresponds to analyzing the error equation directly. We consider the time Fourier transform

$$\hat{u}(x, k) = \mathcal{F}_t(u)(x, k) := \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u(x, t)e^{-itk} dt,$$

with all functions under consideration vanishing for $t < 0$. Taking this Fourier transform of the governing equations in (2) in the time direction gives¹

$$\begin{cases} -k^2 \hat{u}_1^n(x, k) - ik\varepsilon \partial_{xx} \hat{u}_1^n(x, k) - \gamma \partial_{xx} \hat{u}_1^n(x, k) = 0, & (x, k) \in \Omega_1 \times \mathbb{K}, \\ \hat{u}_1^n(L, k) = \hat{u}_2^{n-1}(L, k), & k \in \mathbb{K}, \\ -k^2 \hat{u}_2^n(x, k) - ik\varepsilon \partial_{xx} \hat{u}_2^n(x, k) - \gamma \partial_{xx} \hat{u}_2^n(x, k) = 0, & (x, k) \in \Omega_2 \times \mathbb{K}, \\ \hat{u}_2^n(0, k) = \hat{u}_1^{n-1}(0, k), & k \in \mathbb{K}, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where k represents the Fourier frequency and \mathbb{K} is the set of all admissible frequencies involved in a practical calculation. Due to the infinity assumption on the subdomains, the subdomain solutions to the governing equation in (3) hence read

$$\hat{u}_1^n = A(k)e^{\lambda(k)x}, \quad \hat{u}_2^n = B(k)e^{-\lambda(k)x}, \quad (4)$$

where $\pm\lambda(k)$ are the solutions to the characteristic equation $-k^2 - (ik\varepsilon + \gamma)\lambda^2 = 0$ and have the following expressions

$$\lambda(k) = \sqrt{-\frac{k^2}{ik\varepsilon + \gamma}} = a(k) + ib(k),$$

with

$$a(k) = \frac{|k| \sqrt{\sqrt{\gamma^2 + \varepsilon^2 k^2} - \gamma}}{\sqrt{2} \sqrt{\gamma^2 + \varepsilon^2 k^2}}, \quad b(k) = \frac{k \sqrt{\sqrt{\gamma^2 + \varepsilon^2 k^2} + \gamma}}{\sqrt{2} \sqrt{\gamma^2 + \varepsilon^2 k^2}}$$

and $b(k)^2 - a(k)^2 = \frac{\gamma k^2}{\gamma^2 + \varepsilon^2 k^2}$, $2a(k)b(k) = \frac{\varepsilon k^3}{\gamma^2 + \varepsilon^2 k^2}$. To satisfy the interface conditions in (3), the subdomain solutions (4) are specified as

$$\hat{u}_1^n(x, k) = \hat{u}_2^{n-1}(L, k)e^{\lambda(k)(x-L)}, \quad \hat{u}_2^n(x, k) = \hat{u}_1^{n-1}(0, k)e^{-\lambda(k)x}.$$

Inserting these solutions into algorithm (3), we obtain by induction

$$\hat{u}_1^{2n}(0, k) = \rho_{cla}^n \hat{u}_1^0(0, k), \quad \hat{u}_2^{2n}(L, k) = \rho_{cla}^n \hat{u}_1^0(L, k),$$

where the convergence factor $\rho_{cla}(k, L)$ of the classical SWR algorithm is given by

$$\rho_{cla}(k, L) := \left| e^{-2\lambda(k)L} \right| = e^{-2a(k)L}. \quad (5)$$

From this convergence factor, we know that an overlap $L > 0$ is necessary for the convergence of the overlapping SWR algorithm (2): if there is no overlap, algorithm (2) does not converge. It should be noted that the overlap accelerates convergence: the larger the overlap, the faster the algorithm converges.

¹Strictly speaking, one should apply the Laplace transform here. However, a Fourier transform can be applied to provide the same convergence factors in a simpler way, as shown in [5].

To achieve fast convergence, we modify the algorithm as follows by applying new transmission conditions

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \partial_{tt}u_1^n(x, t) - \varepsilon\partial_{txx}u_1^n(x, t) - \gamma\partial_{xx}u_1^n(x, t) = f(x, t), \quad (x, t) \in \Omega_1 \times (0, T], \\ \partial_x u_1^n(L, t) + S_1 u_1^n(L, t) = \partial_x u_2^{n-1}(L, t) + S_1 u_2^{n-1}(L, t), \quad t \in (0, T], \\ u_1^n(x, 0) = \psi_1(x), \quad x \in \Omega_1, \\ \partial_t u_1^n(x, 0) = \psi_2(x), \quad x \in \Omega_1, \\ \partial_{tt}u_2^n(x, t) - \varepsilon\partial_{txx}u_2^n(x, t) - \gamma\partial_{xx}u_2^n(x, t) = f(x, t), \quad (x, t) \in \Omega_2 \times (0, T], \\ -\partial_x u_2^n(0, t) + S_2 u_2^n(0, t) = -\partial_x u_1^{n-1}(0, t) + S_2 u_1^{n-1}(0, t), \quad t \in (0, T], \\ u_2^n(x, 0) = \psi_1(x), \quad x \in \Omega_2, \\ \partial_t u_2^n(x, 0) = \psi_2(x), \quad x \in \Omega_2, \end{array} \right. \quad (6)$$

where S_j , $j = 1, 2$, are linear operators in time that we will determine subsequently to get the best possible performance of the new Schwarz algorithm. As for the classical SWR method, taking a Fourier transform in time for $f = 0$, we obtain

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -k^2 \hat{u}_1^n(x, k) - ik\varepsilon\partial_{xx}\hat{u}_1^n(x, k) - \gamma\partial_{xx}\hat{u}_1^n(x, k) = 0, \quad (x, k) \in \Omega_1 \times \mathbb{K}, \\ \partial_x \hat{u}_1^n(L, k) + \sigma_1 \hat{u}_1^n(L, k) = \partial_x \hat{u}_2^{n-1}(L, k) + \sigma_1 \hat{u}_2^{n-1}(L, k), \quad k \in \mathbb{K}, \\ -k^2 \hat{u}_2^n(x, k) - ik\varepsilon\partial_{xx}\hat{u}_2^n(x, k) - \gamma\partial_{xx}\hat{u}_2^n(x, k) = 0, \quad (x, k) \in \Omega_2 \times \mathbb{K}, \\ -\partial_x \hat{u}_2^n(0, k) + \sigma_2 \hat{u}_2^n(0, k) = -\partial_x \hat{u}_1^{n-1}(0, k) + \sigma_2 \hat{u}_1^{n-1}(0, k), \quad k \in \mathbb{K}, \end{array} \right.$$

where $\sigma_1(k)$ and $\sigma_2(k)$ are Fourier symbols of the operators S_1 and S_2 , respectively. A discussion similar to the analysis for the classical SWR reveals that the subdomain solutions now satisfy

$$\hat{u}_1^{2n}(0, k) = \rho_{opt}^n \hat{u}_1^0(0, k), \quad \hat{u}_2^{2n}(L, k) = \rho_{opt}^n \hat{u}_2^0(L, k), \quad (7)$$

where the new convergence factor ρ_{opt} is given by

$$\rho_{opt}(k, L, \sigma_1, \sigma_2) := \left| \frac{-\lambda + \sigma_1(k)}{\lambda + \sigma_1(k)} \cdot \frac{-\lambda + \sigma_2(k)}{\lambda + \sigma_2(k)} \right| \cdot |e^{-2\lambda L}|.$$

The convergence factor ρ_{opt} differs from the classical version ρ_{cla} in the term in front of the exponential term, which can be controlled such that the SWR method (6) converges as fast as possible.

Choosing the symbols $\sigma_{1,2}$ as

$$\sigma_{1,2} = \lambda(k) = \sqrt{-\frac{k^2}{ik\varepsilon + \gamma}}, \quad (8)$$

the new convergence factor vanishes identically, $\rho_{opt} \equiv 0$, and in this case the algorithm (6) will converge in two iterations [12]. We remark here that if the damping coefficient $\varepsilon = 0$, i.e., the model problem (1) degenerates to a wave equation, it holds $\lambda(k) = \frac{ik}{\sqrt{\gamma}}$.

The optimal symbols $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \lambda(k) = \frac{ik}{\sqrt{\gamma}}$ then correspond to local operators that can be implemented easily, and the OSWR algorithm for the wave equation can converge in two iterations, as shown in [19].

In fact, to obtain the transmission operators S_1 and S_2 , we need to back-transform the Fourier symbols σ_1 and σ_2 from the Fourier frequency domain into the operators in the physical domain

$$S_1(u_1^n) = \mathcal{F}_t^{-1}(\sigma_1 \hat{u}_1^n), \quad S_2(u_2^n) = \mathcal{F}_t^{-1}(\sigma_2 \hat{u}_2^n),$$

where \mathcal{F}_t^{-1} denotes the inverse Fourier transform. The use of the optimal symbols in (8) corresponds to nonlocal operators that incur a heavy computational load in each step of the algorithm, due to the convolution that must be evaluated for interface communication. Obviously, if the symbols $\sigma_{1,2}$ were polynomials in ik , the corresponding operators $S_{1,2}$ would be local differential operators in t , thereby simplifying the implementation of the information exchange. In what follows, we would like to approximate the optimal Fourier symbols $\sigma_{1,2}$ by linear functions of ik as follows

$$\sigma_1^{app}(k) = p_1 + q_1 \cdot ik, \quad \sigma_2^{app}(k) = p_2 + q_2 \cdot ik,$$

which correspond to the following interface operators

$$S_1 = p_1 + q_1 \partial_t, \quad S_2 = p_2 + q_2 \partial_t.$$

The convergence factor of the OSWR algorithm (6) now reads

$$\rho(k, L, p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2) = \left| \frac{\lambda - p_1 - q_1 \cdot ik}{\lambda + p_1 + q_1 \cdot ik} \cdot \frac{\lambda - p_2 - q_2 \cdot ik}{\lambda + p_2 + q_2 \cdot ik} \right| \cdot |e^{-2\lambda L}|.$$

The OSWR methods then choose the free parameters $p_i \geq 0, q_i \geq 0, i = 1, 2$, towards the best possible performance, by minimizing the convergence factor over all frequencies relevant to the problem

$$\min_{p_i \geq 0, q_i \geq 0} \max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho(k, L, p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2), \quad (9)$$

where we comment that only positive Fourier frequencies should be considered, i.e. $\mathbb{K} = [k_{min}, k_{max}]$, since ρ is symmetric in k due to the presence of the damping term $-\varepsilon \partial_{t,x,x} u$, which essentially differs from the case of typical wave equation where the convergence factor is asymmetric in k .

However, the function $\lambda(k)$ depends on k in a complicated fashion, which makes it very hard to optimize the convergence factor ρ_{opt} directly. As a help, we therefore propose, highlighted by the fact $\lambda(k) \sim \sqrt{\frac{k}{2\varepsilon}}(1+i)$ as $k \rightarrow +\infty$, the following approximation for sufficiently large $k > 0$

$$\tilde{\rho}(k, L, p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2) = \left| \frac{\tilde{\lambda} - p_1 - q_1 \cdot ik}{\tilde{\lambda} + p_1 + q_1 \cdot ik} \cdot \frac{\tilde{\lambda} - p_2 - q_2 \cdot ik}{\tilde{\lambda} + p_2 + q_2 \cdot ik} \right| \cdot |e^{-2\tilde{\lambda}L}|,$$

where $\tilde{\lambda}(k) = \tilde{a}(1 + i)$ with $\tilde{a} = \sqrt{\frac{k}{2\varepsilon}}$. The approximation error is shown below.

Lemma 1 (Approximation error of the convergence factor). *For sufficiently large $k > 0$, the difference between the convergence factor ρ and its approximation $\tilde{\rho}$ satisfies the following estimates:*

(1) *When there is a small overlap $L > 0$:*

$$\begin{aligned} & |\rho(k, L, p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2) - \tilde{\rho}(k, L, p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2)| \\ &= \frac{\gamma L}{\sqrt{2\varepsilon^{\frac{3}{2}}\sqrt{k}}} - \frac{\gamma(q_1 + q_2)L}{\varepsilon^2 q_1 q_2 k} + O(L^2 + \frac{L^2}{\sqrt{k}} + \frac{L^2}{k}). \end{aligned}$$

(2) *When there is no overlap ($L = 0$):*

$$|\rho(k, 0, p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2) - \tilde{\rho}(k, 0, p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2)| = \frac{\gamma(q_1 + q_2)}{\sqrt{2\varepsilon^{\frac{3}{2}} q_1 q_2 k^{\frac{3}{2}}}} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right).$$

Proof. A direct expansion of the difference for large k yields

$$\begin{aligned} & |\rho(k, L, p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2) - \tilde{\rho}(k, L, p_1, p_2, q_1, q_2)| \\ &= e^{-\sqrt{\frac{2k}{\varepsilon}}L} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2}\gamma L}{2\varepsilon^{\frac{3}{2}}} \frac{1}{k^{\frac{1}{2}}} - \left(\frac{\gamma(q_1 + q_2)L}{\varepsilon^2 q_1 q_2} - \frac{\gamma^2 L^2}{4\varepsilon^3} \right) \frac{1}{k} - \Psi \frac{1}{k^{\frac{3}{2}}} + O\left(\frac{1}{k^2}\right) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\Psi = \frac{\sqrt{2}\gamma(q_1 + q_2)}{2\varepsilon^{\frac{3}{2}} q_1 q_2} - \frac{\sqrt{2}\gamma(4q_1^2 + 4q_2^2 + 8q_1 q_2 + 3\gamma q_1^2 q_2^2)}{8\varepsilon^{\frac{5}{2}} q_1^2 q_2^2} L + \frac{\sqrt{2}\gamma^2(q_1 + q_2)}{4\varepsilon^{\frac{7}{2}} q_1 q_2} L^2 - \frac{\sqrt{2}\gamma^3}{24\varepsilon^{\frac{9}{2}}} L^3.$$

Taking the limit $L \rightarrow 0$ in (10) directly gives assertion (2). For small L , we substitute the Taylor expansion

$$e^{-\sqrt{\frac{2k}{\varepsilon}}L} = 1 - \sqrt{\frac{2k}{\varepsilon}}L + \frac{1}{\varepsilon}kL^2 + O(L^3)$$

into (10) and collect terms with respect to k and L , which leads to assertion (1). \square

When a uniform temporal mesh of size τ is applied, the largest Fourier frequency k_{max} can be estimated as $k_{max} = \frac{\pi}{\tau}$, and the smallest Fourier frequency can be estimated as $k_{min} = \frac{\pi}{T}$ [17]. When an overlapping domain decomposition is applied, we assume the overlap L is $L = C_1 h$ with h being the uniform spatial mesh size. Note that for a particular discretization, which should satisfy a stability or an accuracy constraint, we then assume $\tau = C_2 h^\delta$, $\delta > 0$. Lemma 1 shows that $\tilde{\rho}$ well approximates the convergence factor ρ at high frequencies. This enables a hybrid analytical strategy for the min-max problem (9): for high frequencies, we analyze the approximation $\tilde{\rho}$ directly, while for low frequencies, where the approximation may be less accurate, we analyze the monotonicity of ρ itself. Integrating these two parts yields an asymptotic

solution to (9) as $\tau \rightarrow 0$, without affecting the final asymptotic results. This methodology, developed in [24, 25], has proven effective in tackling complex min-max problems arising in optimized Schwarz methods. In practice, the temporal mesh size τ must be chosen sufficiently small (depending on the problem) to ensure this asymptotic regime is valid.

3 Robin transmission conditions

Although the model problem (1) is a wave type equation, the occurrence of the damping term $-\varepsilon \partial_{txx} u$ leads to parabolic properties [3, 30]. This sparks our interest in the performance of the Robin transmission conditions, even if they are not efficient for the hyperbolic equations.

Assuming $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = p$, i.e., taking $p_1 = p_2 = p, q_1 = q_2 = 0$, the convergence factor of the OSWR algorithm (6) becomes

$$\rho_R(k, L, p) = \left| \frac{\lambda(k) - p}{\lambda(k) + p} \right|^2 \cdot \left| e^{-2\lambda(k)L} \right| = \frac{(a(k) - p)^2 + b(k)^2}{(a(k) + p)^2 + b(k)^2} \cdot e^{-2a(k)L},$$

and the approximate convergence factor now reads

$$\tilde{\rho}_R(k, L, p) = \left| \frac{\tilde{\lambda}(k) - p}{\tilde{\lambda}(k) + p} \right|^2 \cdot \left| e^{-2\tilde{\lambda}(k)L} \right| = \frac{(\tilde{a}(k) - p)^2 + \tilde{a}(k)^2}{(\tilde{a}(k) + p)^2 + \tilde{a}(k)^2} \cdot e^{-2\tilde{a}(k)L}. \quad (11)$$

The optimized parameter p^* is thus the solution of the min-max problem

$$\min_{p>0} \max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_R(k, L, p). \quad (12)$$

However, directly solving the min-max problem (12) is highly challenging due to the complexity of the expression for ρ_R and the difficulty in computing its derivatives. To circumvent this, we adopt an alternative approach: first, we determine the optimized parameter p^* by solving the equi-oscillation equation

$$\rho_R(k_{\min}, L, p^*) = \rho_R(\tilde{k}^*, L, p^*), \quad (13)$$

where \tilde{k}^* is the point at which $\rho_R(k, L, p^*)$ attains its maximum. We then demonstrate that this p^* indeed solves the original min-max problem (12) by analyzing the behavior of ρ_R for parameters different from p^* .

Thus, the problem reduces to characterizing the maximum points of ρ_R . Given that Lemma 1 establishes $\tilde{\rho}_R$ as an accurate high-frequency approximation of ρ_R , we can achieve this by examining the extremum points of $\tilde{\rho}_R$.

Lemma 2. *For $0 < p < \frac{\sqrt{2}-1}{L}$, the approximate convergence factor $\tilde{\rho}_R(k, L, p)$ defined in (11), when regarded as a function in $k \in \mathbb{K}$, reaches its unique local maximum at*

$$\bar{k} = \frac{\varepsilon p (1 + \sqrt{1 - 2pL - p^2 L^2})}{L},$$

and reaches its unique local minimum at

$$\underline{k} = \frac{\varepsilon p(1 - \sqrt{1 - 2pL - p^2L^2})}{L}.$$

Proof. Calculating the partial derivative of $\tilde{\rho}_R(k, h, p)$ in k gives

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\rho}_R(k, L, p)}{\partial k} = -\frac{Lk^2 - \varepsilon pk + 2\varepsilon^2 p^3 + \varepsilon^2 p^4 L}{\sqrt{2\varepsilon k}(\sqrt{2\varepsilon k p} + \varepsilon p^2 + k)^2} e^{-\sqrt{\frac{2k}{\varepsilon}}L}.$$

The assertion then follows from an analysis of the derivative. \square

Theorem 1. *The equi-oscillation problem (13) between k_{min} and $\tilde{k}^* = Ch^{-\theta}$, $0 < \theta < 2$, is asymptotically solved for h small by ²*

$$p^* = \begin{cases} 2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{4}} C^{\frac{1}{4}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}} h^{-\frac{\theta}{4}}, & \text{if } 0 < \theta < \frac{4}{3}, \\ 2^{-2} \varepsilon^{-1} C^{\frac{1}{4}} (\sqrt{C_1^2 C^{\frac{3}{2}} + 2^{\frac{9}{2}} \varepsilon^{\frac{3}{2}} a_{min}} - C_1 C^{\frac{3}{4}}) h^{-\frac{1}{3}}, & \text{if } \theta = \frac{4}{3}, \\ 2^{\frac{3}{2}} \varepsilon^{\frac{1}{2}} C^{\frac{1}{2}} a_{min} C_1^{-1} h^{-1+\frac{\theta}{2}}, & \text{if } \frac{4}{3} < \theta < 2, \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where $a_{min} = a(k_{min})$, $L = C_1 h$.

Proof. Given the complexity of the convergence factor ρ_R , directly solving the equi-oscillation problem (13) is infeasible. We therefore seek a solution in an asymptotic sense. Since numerical test shows that p^* goes to infinity as $L \rightarrow 0$, we make the ansatz $p^* = C_p L^{-\alpha}$ with $0 < \alpha < \frac{\theta}{2}$. Noting that $L = C_1 h$, expanding the left-hand side of (13) gives

$$\rho_R(k_{min}, L, p^*) = 1 - \frac{4a_{min}}{C_p} C_1^\alpha h^\alpha + O(h^{2\alpha}).$$

While the right-hand side can be expanded, using Lemma 1, as

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_R(\tilde{k}^*, L, p^*) &= \tilde{\rho}_R(\tilde{k}^*, L, p^*) + O(h^{1+\frac{\theta}{2}}) \\ &= 1 - 4\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{2C}} C_p C_1^{-\alpha} h^{\frac{\theta}{2}-\alpha} - \sqrt{\frac{2C}{\varepsilon}} C_1 h^{1-\frac{\theta}{2}} + O(h^{\min\{\theta-2\alpha, 2-\theta, 1-\alpha\}}). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Since (13) holds for all $h > 0$, we must have equality of the leading terms. Note that when $\alpha = \frac{\theta}{2} - \alpha = 1 - \frac{\theta}{2}$, i.e., $\alpha = \frac{1}{3}$, $\theta = \frac{4}{3}$, the terms related to h in (15) have the same exponents. If the second term in (15) is dominant, i.e., $\frac{\theta}{2} - \alpha < 1 - \frac{\theta}{2}$, then equating the leading terms of the two series expansions yields $\alpha = \frac{\theta}{2} - \alpha$. These two conditions

²Noting that \tilde{k}^* is not necessarily contained in $\mathbb{K} = [k_{min}, k_{max}]$.

imply $\theta < \frac{4}{3}$. Similar analysis shows that, if the third term in (15) is dominant, one should have $\theta > \frac{4}{3}$. Therefore, we have

$$\frac{4a_{min}}{C_p} C_1^\alpha h^\alpha = \begin{cases} 4\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{2C}} C_p C_1^{-\alpha} h^{\frac{\theta}{2}-\alpha}, & \text{if } 0 < \theta < \frac{4}{3}, \\ \sqrt{\frac{2C}{\varepsilon}} C_1 h^{1-\frac{\theta}{2}} + 4\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{2C}} C_p C_1^{-\alpha} h^{\frac{\theta}{2}-\alpha}, & \text{if } \theta = \frac{4}{3}, \\ \sqrt{\frac{2C}{\varepsilon}} C_1 h^{1-\frac{\theta}{2}}, & \text{if } \frac{4}{3} < \theta < 2, \end{cases}$$

which leads to the solutions

$$\begin{cases} \alpha^* = \frac{\theta}{4}, C_p^* = 2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{4}} C_1^{\frac{\theta}{4}} C^{\frac{1}{2}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}}, & \text{if } 0 < \theta < \frac{4}{3}, \\ \alpha^* = \frac{1}{3}, C_p^* = 2^{-2} \varepsilon^{-1} C_1^{\frac{\theta}{4}} C^{\frac{1}{4}} (\sqrt{C_1^2 C^{\frac{3}{2}} + 2^{\frac{9}{2}} \varepsilon^{\frac{3}{2}} a_{min}} - C_1 C^{\frac{3}{4}}), & \text{if } \theta = \frac{4}{3}, \\ \alpha^* = 1 - \frac{\theta}{2}, C_p^* = 2^{\frac{3}{2}} \varepsilon^{\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{-\frac{\theta}{2}} C^{-\frac{1}{2}} a_{min}, & \text{if } \frac{4}{3} < \theta < 2. \end{cases}$$

Thus, the parameter p^* in (14) is obtained. \square

Theorem 2 (Robin transmission condition, overlapping case). *Let $L = C_1 h$ and $\tau = C_2 h^\delta$. The min-max problem (12) is asymptotically solved for h sufficiently small by*

$$p^* = \begin{cases} a_{min}^{\frac{2}{3}} C_1^{-\frac{1}{3}} h^{-\frac{1}{3}}, & \text{if } \delta > \frac{4}{3} \text{ or } \delta = \frac{4}{3} \text{ and } C_1 \geq C_r, \\ \tilde{C}_p C_1^{-\frac{1}{3}} h^{-\frac{1}{3}}, & \text{if } \delta = \frac{4}{3} \text{ and } C_1 < C_r, \\ a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}} (\frac{2\pi}{\varepsilon C_2})^{\frac{1}{4}} h^{-\frac{\delta}{4}}, & \text{if } \delta < \frac{4}{3}, \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where $\tilde{C}_p = \frac{C_1^{\frac{1}{3}} \pi^{\frac{1}{4}}}{4\varepsilon C_2} \left(\sqrt{C_1^2 \pi^{\frac{3}{2}} + 2^{\frac{9}{2}} (\varepsilon C_2)^{\frac{3}{2}} a_{min}} - C_1 \pi^{\frac{3}{4}} \right)$ and $C_r = (\frac{2\varepsilon C_2}{\pi})^{\frac{3}{4}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

The maximum of the corresponding convergence factor ρ_R has the following asymptotic expansion for h small

$$\max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_R(k, L, p^*) = \begin{cases} 1 - 4a_{min}^{\frac{1}{3}} C_1^{\frac{1}{3}} h^{\frac{1}{3}} + O(h^{\frac{2}{3}}), & \text{if } \delta > \frac{4}{3} \text{ or } \delta = \frac{4}{3} \text{ and } C_1 \geq C_r, \\ 1 - \frac{4a_{min}}{C_p} C_1^{\frac{1}{3}} h^{\frac{1}{3}} + O(h^{\frac{2}{3}}), & \text{if } \delta = \frac{4}{3} \text{ and } C_1 < C_r, \\ 1 - 4a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}} (\frac{\varepsilon C_2}{2\pi})^{\frac{1}{4}} h^{\frac{\delta}{4}} + O(h^{\frac{\delta}{2}}), & \text{if } \delta < \frac{4}{3}. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Proof. We separate the proof into the following four steps.

As the first step, we, based on Theorem 1, determine the solution p^* to the equio-oscillation problem in the admissible frequency domain $\mathbb{K} = [k_{min}, k_{max}]$. Similar to the previous analysis, we assume again $p^* = C_p L^{-\alpha}$. From Lemmas 1 and 2, we know that the location of the unique interior maximum of $\rho_R(k, L, p)$ in the asymptotic sense is

$$\bar{k}^* := \bar{k}(p^*) = \frac{\varepsilon p^* (1 + \sqrt{1 - 2p^* L - (p^*)^2 L^2})}{L} = 2\varepsilon C_p (C_1 h)^{-(1+\alpha)} + O(h^{-2\alpha}).$$

Note that, in a numerical calculation, an estimate for the maximum frequency is $k_{max} = \frac{\pi}{C_2 h^\delta}$. We thus need to compare the positions of the maximum frequency k_{max} and the local maximum point \bar{k}^* .

If $k_{max} \geq \bar{k}^*$, i.e., $\pi(C_2 h^\delta)^{-1} \geq 2\varepsilon C_p (C_1 h)^{-(1+\alpha)}$, requiring that $\delta > 1 + \alpha$ or $\delta = 1 + \alpha$ and $C_1 \geq (2\varepsilon C_p C_2 / \pi)^{\frac{1}{1+\alpha}}$, we should equi-oscillate between k_{min} and \bar{k}^* . By equating the leading terms of $\tilde{k}^* = C h^{-\theta}$ and $\bar{k}^* = 2\varepsilon C_p (C_1 h)^{-(1+\alpha)} + O(h^{-2\alpha})$, we obtain $\theta = 1 + \alpha$, $C = 2\varepsilon C_p C_1^{-(1+\alpha)}$ in Theorem 1, and equation (15) now reads $\rho_R(\tilde{k}^*, L, p^*) = 1 - 4C_p^{\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{\frac{1-\alpha}{2}} h^{\frac{1-\alpha}{2}} + O(h^{1-\alpha})$, which leads to

$$\alpha^* = \frac{1}{3}, C_p^* = a_{min}^{\frac{2}{3}}. \quad (18)$$

Using these results, one finds that $k_{max} \geq \bar{k}^*$ is equivalent to $\delta > \frac{4}{3}$, or $\delta = \frac{4}{3}$ and $C_1 \geq (2\varepsilon C_2 / \pi)^{\frac{3}{4}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}} =: C_r$.

Then, when $\delta < \frac{4}{3}$, or $\delta = \frac{4}{3}$ and $C_1 < C_r$, we have $k_{max} < \bar{k}^*$, and we should equi-oscillate between k_{min} and k_{max} . Choosing $\tilde{k}^* = k_{max} = \frac{\pi}{C_2 h^\delta}$ in Theorem 1, one finds

$$\begin{cases} \alpha^* = \frac{1}{3}, C_p^* = \tilde{C}_p, & \text{if } \delta = \frac{4}{3} \text{ and } C_1 < C_r, \\ \alpha^* = \frac{\delta}{4}, C_p^* = a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{2\pi C_1^\delta}{\varepsilon C_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}}, & \text{if } \delta < \frac{4}{3}, \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

where $\tilde{C}_p = \frac{C_1^{\frac{3}{4}} \pi^{\frac{1}{4}}}{4\varepsilon C_2} \left(\sqrt{C_1^2 \pi^{\frac{3}{2}} + 2^{\frac{9}{2}} (\varepsilon C_2)^{\frac{3}{2}} a_{min}} - C_1 \pi^{\frac{3}{4}} \right)$. Combining equations (18) and (19), one finds the expression of the optimized parameter as shown in (16).

In the second step, we show that $\rho_R(k, L, p^*)$ attains its maximum asymptotically at either $k = k_{min}$ or $k = \bar{k}^*$. Here we only show the detailed proof for the first case, $k_{max} > \bar{k}^*$, and the other two cases are similar. Now, we need to show that for $k_{min} < k < \underline{k}$, $\rho_R(k, L, p^*)$ decreases in k , where \underline{k} is defined in Lemma 2 with $p = p^* = a_{min}^{\frac{2}{3}} (C_1 h)^{-\frac{1}{3}}$, and

$$\underline{k} \sim \varepsilon a_{min}^{\frac{4}{3}} L^{-\frac{2}{3}} + O(1). \quad (20)$$

We rewrite $\rho_R(k, L, p^*) = \rho_R(k, 0, p^*) \rho_{cla}(k, L)$ with $\rho_R(k, 0, p) = \frac{(a(k)-p)^2 + b(k)^2}{(a(k)+p)^2 + b(k)^2}$. Let us investigate first the properties of $a(k)$ and $b(k)$. We claim that both $a(k)$ and $b(k)$ are monotonically increasing functions in k , since

$$\frac{\partial a(k)}{\partial k} = \frac{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\eta - \gamma}(\eta^2 + \eta\gamma + 2\gamma^2)}{4\eta^3} > 0, \quad \frac{\partial b(k)}{\partial k} = \frac{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\eta + \gamma}(\eta^2 - \eta\gamma + 2\gamma^2)}{4\eta^3} > 0,$$

where $\eta(k) = \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 k^2 + \gamma^2}$. Moreover, using (20), we obtain $a(\underline{k}) = 2^{-\frac{1}{2}} a_{min}^{\frac{2}{3}} (C_1 h)^{-\frac{1}{3}} + O(h^{\frac{1}{3}}) < p^*$. Therefore, for $k_{min} < k < \underline{k}$, we have that $a(k) > a_{min}$, $a(k) - p^* < 0$ and $(a(k) - p^*)^2$ is decreasing. However, it is still difficult to directly analyze the monotonicity of $\rho_R(k, 0, p^*)$. To this end, we propose to analyze using asymptotic

analysis as follows. Assume δ_k is a small increment of the frequency k , we then have, by a direct calculation

$$\rho_R(k + \delta_k, 0, p^*) = \rho_R(k, 0, p^*) + \begin{cases} -\frac{\sqrt{2}((\varepsilon^2 C_k^2 + 2\gamma^2)\sqrt{\varepsilon^2 C_k^2 + \gamma^2 - 2\gamma^3})}{C_p^*(\varepsilon^2 C_k^2 + \gamma^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}\sqrt{\varepsilon^2 C_k^2 + \gamma^2 - \gamma}} L^{\frac{1}{3}} \delta_k + O(L^{\frac{2}{3}} \delta_k), & \text{if } \vartheta = 0, \\ -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon C_k C_p^*}} L^{\frac{1}{3} + \frac{\vartheta}{2}} \delta_k + O(L^{\min\{\frac{2}{3}, \frac{1}{3} + \frac{3\vartheta}{2}\}} \delta_k), & \text{if } 0 < \vartheta < \frac{2}{3}, \\ \frac{\sqrt{2\varepsilon C_p^*}(C_k - \varepsilon(C_p^*)^2)(C_k + \varepsilon(C_p^*)^2 + \sqrt{2\varepsilon C_k C_p^*})}{\sqrt{C_k}(\varepsilon(C_p^*)^2 \sqrt{2\varepsilon C_k C_p^*} + C_k)^3} L^{\frac{2}{3}} \delta_k + O(L^{\frac{4}{3}} \delta_k), & \text{if } \vartheta = \frac{2}{3}, \\ \sqrt{2\varepsilon C_p^*} C_k^{-\frac{3}{2}} L^{\frac{3\vartheta}{2} - \frac{1}{3}} \delta_k + O(L^{2\vartheta - \frac{2}{3}} \delta_k), & \text{if } \frac{2}{3} < \vartheta < \frac{4}{3}, \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

with $k = C_k L^{-\vartheta}$. Together with equation (20), and noting the fact that L is small, equation (21) shows that in the asymptotic sense $\rho_R(k, 0, p^*)$ is monotonically decreasing in k for $k \in (k_{min}, \bar{k})$. Using the decreasing property of $\rho_{cla}(k, L)$ for $k > 0$, we obtain, for sufficiently small h , that $\rho_R(k, L, p^*)$, as the product of two decreasing functions, decreases in k for $k_{min} < k < \bar{k}$. This implies that the lowest frequency k_{min} is a local maximum point for h small.

When $k > \bar{k}$, from Lemma 1 we know that $\rho_R(k, L, p^*) = \tilde{\rho}_R(k, L, p^*) + O(h^{\frac{2}{3}})$, and hence $\rho_R(k, L, p^*)$ attains its unique interior maximum asymptotically at \bar{k}^* .

In the third step, we show that p^* in (16) solves the min-max problem (12) in an asymptotic sense. Using the idea from Gander and Xu [24, 25], we aim at showing that any parameters differing from p^* in the asymptotic sense would lead to a maximum value of ρ_R greater than $\rho_R(k_{min}, L, p^*)$. Again, we show only the detailed proof for the first case, i.e. $k_{max} > \bar{k}^*$, and the other two cases can be obtained similarly. Assuming $p = C_p L^{-\alpha}$, we only need to show that if $\alpha \neq \alpha^* = \frac{1}{3}$, or $C_p \neq C_p^*$, it holds $\max_k \rho_R(k, L, p) > \max_k \rho_R(k, L, p^*)$ for h small enough. When $\alpha < \alpha^*$, an expansion for h small gives

$$\rho_R(\bar{k}, L, p) = 1 - 4\sqrt{C_p} C_1^{\frac{1-\alpha}{2}} h^{\frac{1-\alpha}{2}} + O(h^{1-\alpha}).$$

Since $\frac{1-\alpha}{2} > \frac{1}{3}$ for $\alpha < \frac{1}{3}$, we conclude that for sufficiently small h it holds

$$\rho_R(\bar{k}, L, p) > \rho_R(\bar{k}, L, p^*) = 1 - O(h^{\frac{1}{3}}).$$

When $\alpha > \alpha^*$, we have for h small

$$\rho_R(k_{min}, L, p) = 1 - \frac{4a_{min}}{C_p} C_1^\alpha h^\alpha + O(h^{\min\{2\alpha, 1\}}),$$

which is definitely greater than $\rho_R(k_{min}, L, p^*)$ for sufficiently small h . We now consider the case $\alpha = \alpha^*$ but $C_p \neq C_p^*$. By the asymptotic expansions above we find that $\rho_R(k_{min}, L, p) > \rho_R(k_{min}, L, p^*)$ if $C_p > C_p^*$ and $\rho_R(\bar{k}, L, p) > \rho_R(\bar{k}, L, p^*)$ if $C_p < C_p^*$.

As the final step, we expand $\rho_R(k_{min}, L, p^*)$ with p^* defined in (16) for h small to obtain the desired results (17). \square

From the proof of Theorem 2, we know that $a(k)$ is monotonically increasing with respect to k . Furthermore, we have the following remarks.

Remark 1. *For h small, the maximum value of the convergence factor $\rho_{cla}(k, L)$ of the classical SWR algorithm defined in (5) has the following asymptotic expansion with $L = C_1 h$*

$$\max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_{cla}(k, L) = 1 - 2a_{min} C_1 h + O(h^2). \quad (22)$$

Similar results can be established for the non-overlapping case (which cannot be simply obtained by taking the limit $L \rightarrow 0$ from the overlapping case since the overlap is related to h), as shown in the following theorem.

Theorem 3 (Robin transmission conditions, non-overlapping case). *For the non-overlapping case, $L = 0$, the parameter p^* given by*

$$p^* = 2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{4}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}} k_{max}^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (23)$$

solves the min-max problem (12) asymptotically for k_{max} large and the corresponding convergence factor satisfies the following estimate

$$\max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_R(k, 0, p^*) = 1 - 4 \cdot 2^{-\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{\frac{1}{4}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}} k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}} + O(k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{2}}).$$

Proof. The convergence factor simplifies to

$$\rho_R(k, 0, p) = \frac{(a(k) - p)^2 + b(k)^2}{(a(k) + p)^2 + b(k)^2},$$

and the free parameter p can then be determined by solving the min-max problem

$$\min_{p > 0} \max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_R(k, 0, p).$$

For k_{max} large enough, if we make ansatz $p^* = c_p^* k_{max}^{\frac{1}{4}}$, then we have

$$\rho_R(k_{min}, 0, p^*) = 1 - 4 \frac{a_{min}}{c_p^*} k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}} + O(k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{2}}), \quad (24a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_R(k_{max}, 0, p^*) &= \tilde{\rho}_R(k_{max}, 0, p^*) + O(k_{max}^{-2}) \\ &= 1 - 2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\varepsilon} c_p^* k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}} + O(k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{2}}). \end{aligned} \quad (24b)$$

Matching the coefficients of the term $k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}}$ in (24a) and (24b), i.e., setting $4 \frac{a_{min}}{c_p^*} = 2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\varepsilon} c_p^*$, one finds $c_p^* = 2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{4}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, which leads to (23).

We now need to show that $\rho_R(k, 0, p)$ attains its maximum asymptotically at either $k = k_{min}$ or $k = k_{max}$. Actually, this analysis is very similar to those for overlapping case, we thus omit the detail.

We are in the position to show that p^* given by (23) solves the min-max problem (12) with $L = 0$ asymptotically. Similar to the previous analysis, assuming that $p = c_p k_{max}^\alpha$, we only need to show that if $\alpha \neq \alpha^* = \frac{1}{4}$ or $c_p \neq c_p^*$, it holds $\max_k \rho_R(k, 0, p) > \max_k \rho_R(k, 0, p^*)$ for sufficiently large k_{max} . When $\alpha < \alpha^*$, we have

$$\rho_R(k_{max}, 0, p) = 1 - 2\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\varepsilon}c_p k_{max}^{-\frac{1-2\alpha}{2}} + O(k_{max}^{-2\alpha}).$$

Since $\frac{1-2\alpha}{2} > \frac{1}{4}$ for $\alpha < \frac{1}{4} = \alpha^*$, we claim that for sufficiently large k_{max} it holds

$$\rho_R(k_{max}, 0, p) > \rho_R(k_{max}, 0, p^*) = 1 - O(k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}}).$$

When $\alpha > \alpha^*$, we consider the convergence factor at k_{min} ,

$$\rho_R(k_{min}, 0, p) = 1 - 4\frac{a_{min}}{c_p}k_{max}^{-\alpha} + O(k_{max}^{-2\alpha}),$$

which is bigger than $\rho_R(k_{min}, 0, p^*)$ if k_{max} is large enough. We then consider the case $\alpha = \alpha^*$ but $c_p \neq c_p^*$. By the asymptotic expansions above we find that if $c_p > c_p^*$, we have $\rho_R(k_{min}, 0, p) > \rho_R(k_{min}, 0, p^*)$, and if $c_p < c_p^*$ we obtain $\rho_R(k_{max}, 0, p) > \rho_R(k_{max}, 0, p^*)$, which concludes the proof of asymptotic optimality.

To show the convergence factor estimate, we only insert c_p^* and α^* into (24a). \square

Now we can compare the asymptotic performance of the algorithm for the two cases with and without overlap.

Remark 2. Assume that the time step size τ is linked to the spatial mesh size h by the relation $\tau = C_2 h^\delta$, a comparison between the results from Theorem 2 and Theorem 3 shows that adding an overlap of size $L = C_1 h$ does improve the performance of the OSWR algorithm, but only for the case $\delta \geq \frac{4}{3}$, whereas for $\delta < \frac{4}{3}$ an overlap proportional to h cannot improve the performance. This occurs because for $\delta < \frac{4}{3}$, the maximum point of the convergence factor lies beyond the largest Fourier frequency. As a result, the equi-oscillation method for solving the min-max problem reduces to the case without overlap, preventing the algorithm from benefiting from the overlap. Specifically, when a centered finite difference scheme is used in space, the temporal and spatial accuracy can be balanced by employing either the Euler scheme with $\tau = h^2$ or the Crank-Nicolson scheme with $\tau = h$. In the ensuing OSWR algorithm with Robin conditions, the Euler scheme admits acceleration through the use of overlap, whereas the Crank-Nicolson scheme does not. This is somehow violating the common knowledge in this community that an overlap will accelerate the subdomain iteration. Similar results have been revealed by Gander and Halpern [17] for parabolic advection reaction diffusion problems, and our results firstly reveal this phenomenon for wave-type equations.

4 Characteristic transmission conditions

For both overlapping and non-overlapping methods, the theoretical results show that if ε is small, the OSWR algorithm converges very slowly. In fact, when ε goes to

zero, the model problem (1) degenerates to a wave equation, which should not be solved using Robin transmission conditions. We thus consider the parameter setting $p_1 = p_2 = 0, q_1 = q_2 = q$, which accounts for a characteristic transmission condition. The corresponding convergence factor can now be reformulated as

$$\rho_C(k, L, q) = \frac{a(k)^2 + (b(k) - qk)^2}{a(k)^2 + (b(k) + qk)^2} e^{-2a(k)L},$$

thus the free parameter q should be determined towards fast convergence by minimizing the maximum of the convergence factor ρ_C over all admissible frequencies

$$\min_{q>0} \max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_C(k, L, q). \quad (25)$$

Correspondingly, the interface transmission operator now reads $q\partial_t \pm \partial_x$, which we call the characteristic transmission condition. Note that Gander et al. [19] showed that this transmission condition has good convergence performance for the one-dimensional wave equation. Below for the viscoelastic equation, we find the optimized parameter involved in the characteristic transmission condition in the OSWR algorithm and establish the corresponding convergence results.

Theorem 4. *The equi-oscillation problem between k_{min} and $\tilde{k}^* = Ch^{-\theta}, 0 < \theta < 2$*

$$\rho_C(k_{min}, L, p^*) = \rho_C(\tilde{k}^*, L, p^*) \quad (26)$$

is asymptotically solved for h small by

$$q^* = \begin{cases} 2^{\frac{3}{4}} (\varepsilon C)^{-\frac{1}{4}} \varsigma_{min}^{-\frac{1}{2}} h^{\frac{\theta}{4}}, & \text{if } 0 < \theta < \frac{4}{3}, \\ (2\varepsilon C)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \varsigma_{min}^{-1} (\sqrt{C^2 C_1^2 + 2^{\frac{3}{2}} (\varepsilon C)^{\frac{1}{2}} \varsigma_{min} + C C_1}) h^{\frac{1}{3}}, & \text{if } \theta = \frac{4}{3}, \\ 2^{\frac{1}{2}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{2}} C^{\frac{1}{2}} C_1 \varsigma_{min}^{-1} h^{1-\frac{\theta}{2}}, & \text{if } \frac{4}{3} < \theta < 2, \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

where $a_{min} = a(k_{min}), b_{min} = b(k_{min}), \varsigma_{min} = 4k_{min}b_{min}/(a_{min}^2 + b_{min}^2)$ and $L = C_1 h$.

Proof. The proof is similar to that of Theorem 1, and is provided in the appendix. \square

For further analysis, we need the following approximate convergence factor

$$\tilde{\rho}_C(k, L, q) = \frac{\tilde{a}(k)^2 + (\tilde{a}(k) - qk)^2}{\tilde{a}(k)^2 + (\tilde{a}(k) + qk)^2} e^{-2\tilde{a}(k)L}. \quad (28)$$

Lemma 3. *For $q > \frac{(1+\sqrt{2})L}{\varepsilon}$, as a function of $k \in \mathbb{K}$ the approximate convergence factor $\tilde{\rho}_C(k, L, q)$ defined in (28) reaches its unique local maximum at*

$$\bar{k} = \frac{\varepsilon q + \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 q^2 - 2\varepsilon q L - L^2}}{\varepsilon q^2 L},$$

and reaches its unique local minimum at

$$\underline{k} = \frac{\varepsilon q - \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 q^2 - 2\varepsilon q L - L^2}}{\varepsilon q^2 L}.$$

Proof. From the derivative of $\tilde{\rho}_C(k, h, p)$ in k we get \bar{k} and \underline{k} by direct calculation. \square

Theorem 5 (Characteristic transmission condition, overlapping case). *Let $L = C_1 h$ and $\tau = C_2 h^\delta$. The min-max problem (25) is asymptotically solved for h sufficiently small by*

$$q^* = \begin{cases} 2^{\frac{4}{3}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{3}} \varsigma_{\min}^{-\frac{2}{3}} C_1^{\frac{1}{3}} h^{\frac{1}{3}}, & \text{if } \delta > \frac{4}{3} \text{ or } \delta = \frac{4}{3} \text{ and } C_1 \geq C_c, \\ \tilde{C}_q C_1^{\frac{1}{3}} h^{\frac{1}{3}}, & \text{if } \delta = \frac{4}{3} \text{ and } C_1 < C_c, \\ 2^{\frac{3}{4}} (\varepsilon \pi)^{-\frac{1}{4}} C_2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varsigma_{\min}^{-\frac{1}{2}} h^{\frac{\delta}{4}}, & \text{if } \delta < \frac{4}{3}, \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

where $C_c = 2^{-\frac{1}{4}} (C_2/\pi)^{\frac{3}{4}} \varepsilon^{\frac{1}{4}} \varsigma_{\min}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, and $\varsigma_{\min} = 4k_{\min} b_{\min} / (a_{\min}^2 + b_{\min}^2)$, $\tilde{C}_q = (2\varepsilon\pi C_2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{-\frac{1}{3}} \varsigma_{\min}^{-1} (\sqrt{\pi^2 C_1^2 + (2C_2)^{\frac{3}{2}} (\varepsilon\pi)^{\frac{1}{2}} \varsigma_{\min} + \pi C_1})$.

The maximum of the corresponding convergence factor ρ_C has the following asymptotic expansion for h small

$$\max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_C(k, L, q^*) = \begin{cases} 1 - 2^{\frac{4}{3}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{3}} \varsigma_{\min}^{\frac{1}{3}} C_1^{\frac{1}{3}} h^{\frac{1}{3}} + O(h^{\frac{2}{3}}), & \text{if } \delta > \frac{4}{3} \text{ or } \delta = \frac{4}{3} \text{ and } C_1 \geq C_c, \\ 1 - \varsigma_{\min} \tilde{C}_q C_1^{\frac{1}{3}} h^{\frac{1}{3}} + O(h^{\frac{2}{3}}), & \text{if } \delta = \frac{4}{3} \text{ and } C_1 < C_c, \\ 1 - 2^{\frac{3}{4}} (\varepsilon \pi)^{-\frac{1}{4}} C_2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varsigma_{\min}^{\frac{1}{2}} h^{\frac{\delta}{4}} + O(h^{\frac{\delta}{2}}), & \text{if } \delta < \frac{4}{3}. \end{cases}$$

Proof. The proof is very similar to that of Theorem 2 and is relegated to the appendix. \square

The following results on determining the optimized transmission parameters when the characteristic transmission conditions are applied to a non-overlapping OSWR method can be proven in a fashion similar to that of Theorem 3, so we also omit the details.

Theorem 6 (Characteristic transmission conditions, non-overlapping case). *For the non-overlapping case, $L = 0$, the parameter q^* given by*

$$q^* = 2^{\frac{3}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{4}} \varsigma_{\min}^{-\frac{1}{2}} k_{\max}^{-\frac{1}{4}} \quad (30)$$

solves the min-max problem (25) asymptotically for k_{\max} large and the corresponding convergence factor satisfies the following estimate for k_{\max} large enough

$$\max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_C(k, 0, q^*) = 1 - 2^{\frac{3}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{4}} \varsigma_{\min}^{\frac{1}{2}} k_{\max}^{-\frac{1}{4}} + O(k_{\max}^{-\frac{1}{2}})$$

where $\varsigma_{\min} = 4k_{\min} b_{\min} / (a_{\min}^2 + b_{\min}^2)$.

Proof. The proof of this theorem is deferred to the appendix. \square

Remark 3. Assume the time step τ is linked to the spatial mesh size h by the relation $\tau = C_2 h^\delta$. Comparing Theorem 5 with Theorem 6, we find that if $\delta < \frac{4}{3}$, an overlap cannot improve the performance of the OSWR algorithm with characteristic transmission conditions, which is similar to the result in Remark 2.

5 Mixed transmission conditions

Previous analyses show that for relatively large ε Robin condition is good, while for relatively small ε characteristic condition is preferable. To incorporate the features of the two transmission conditions mentioned above, we hope to design a unified form of transmission conditions that can deal with arbitrary ε well. We thus choose $p_1 = p_2 = p, q_1 = q_2 = q$, the convergence factor simplifies to

$$\rho_M(k, L, p, q) = \frac{(a(k) - p)^2 + (b(k) - qk)^2}{(a(k) + p)^2 + (b(k) + qk)^2} e^{-2a(k)L}.$$

The corresponding interface transmission operators are $S_1 = S_2 = p + q\partial_t$, which we call the mixed transmission condition since it is a mix of Robin and characteristic conditions. The free parameters p and q then should be determined by solving the min-max problem

$$\min_{p>0, q>0} \max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_M(k, L, p, q). \quad (31)$$

However, it is not an easy task, and we need help from the following approximate convergence factor

$$\tilde{\rho}_M(k, L, p, q) = \frac{(\tilde{a}(k) - p)^2 + (\tilde{a}(k) - qk)^2}{(\tilde{a}(k) + p)^2 + (\tilde{a}(k) + qk)^2} e^{-2\tilde{a}(k)L}, \quad (32)$$

which has the properties below.

Lemma 4. As a function of k , the approximate convergence factor $\tilde{\rho}_M(k, L, p, q)$ defined in (32) has four critical points for $k > 0$ at which it attains local extrema: two local minima at $k = \underline{k}_1$ and $k = \underline{k}_2$, and two local maxima at $k = \bar{k}_1$ and $k = \bar{k}_2$. Their asymptotic behaviors for small L are given by:

$$\underline{k}_1 \sim \varepsilon p^2, \quad \bar{k}_1 \sim \frac{p}{q}, \quad \underline{k}_2 \sim \frac{1}{\varepsilon q^2}, \quad \bar{k}_2 \sim \frac{2}{Lq}. \quad (33)$$

Proof. The change of variables

$$\tilde{k} = \sqrt{\frac{2k}{\varepsilon}} L, \quad \tilde{p} = 2Lp, \quad \tilde{q} = \frac{\varepsilon q}{L}$$

reduces the approximate convergence factor to

$$\tilde{\rho}_M(\tilde{k}, \tilde{p}, \tilde{q}) = \frac{(\tilde{k} - \tilde{p})^2 + (\tilde{k} - \tilde{q}\tilde{k}^2)^2}{(\tilde{k} + \tilde{p})^2 + (\tilde{k} + \tilde{q}\tilde{k}^2)^2} e^{-\tilde{k}}.$$

By computing the derivative with respect to \tilde{k} and setting it to zero, we find that the extreme points correspond to the roots of the polynomial

$$P(\tilde{k}) = \tilde{q}^4 \tilde{k}^8 - 4\tilde{q}^3 \tilde{k}^6 + (2\tilde{p}^2 \tilde{q}^2 + (-12\tilde{q}^2 - 8\tilde{q})\tilde{p} + 8\tilde{q} + 4)\tilde{k}^4 + (12\tilde{p}^2 \tilde{q} - 8\tilde{p})\tilde{k}^2 + \tilde{p}^3(\tilde{p} + 4).$$

Following the approach in Theorem 4.12 in [7], we introduce $X = \tilde{q}\tilde{k}^2$, which transforms $P(\tilde{k})$ into

$$P(X) = X^4 - 4X^3 + (2\tilde{p}^2 - 12\tilde{p} - \frac{8\tilde{p}}{\tilde{q}} + \frac{8}{\tilde{q}} + \frac{4}{\tilde{q}^2})X^2 + (12\tilde{p}^2 - \frac{8\tilde{p}}{\tilde{q}})X + \tilde{p}^3(\tilde{p} + 4).$$

For sufficiently large \tilde{q} , small $\tilde{p}\tilde{q}$, and small L , the dominant part of $P(X)$ is

$$P_0(X) = X^4 - 4X^3 + \frac{8}{\tilde{q}}X^2 - \frac{8\tilde{p}}{\tilde{q}}X + 4\tilde{p}^3,$$

which admits four distinct positive roots X_j ($j = 1, \dots, 4$) with the asymptotic behavior:

$$X_1 \sim \frac{\tilde{p}^2 \tilde{q}}{2}, X_2 \sim \tilde{p}, X_3 \sim \frac{2}{\tilde{q}}, X_4 \sim 4.$$

A perturbation argument then implies that, for sufficiently small L , the polynomial $P(\tilde{k})$ also possesses four distinct positive roots. Recalling that $\tilde{k} = \sqrt{\frac{X}{\tilde{q}}}$, we obtain their asymptotic behavior as

$$\tilde{k}_1 \sim \frac{\tilde{p}}{\sqrt{2}}, \tilde{k}_2 \sim \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{p}}{\tilde{q}}}, \tilde{k}_3 \sim \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\tilde{q}}, \tilde{k}_4 \sim \frac{2}{\sqrt{\tilde{q}}},$$

Reverting to the original variables yields the stated extreme points stated in (33). \square

Similar to the Robin transmission conditions where the min-max problem (11) is solved by a two-point equi-oscillation, numerical investigation shows that the min-max problem (31) is solved by a three-point equi-oscillation, as illustrated in Fig. 1. We thus first determine the optimized parameters p^* and q^* by solving the three-point equi-oscillation problem

$$\rho_M(k_{min}, L, p^*, q^*) = \rho_M(\tilde{k}_1^*, L, p^*, q^*) = \rho_M(\tilde{k}_2^*, L, p^*, q^*), \quad (34)$$

where \tilde{k}_1^* and \tilde{k}_2^* are the two local maximum points of ρ_M , then show the optimality of the resulting parameters.

Fig. 1: Illustration of the equi-oscillation property. Left: $\tau = h$ ($k_{max} < \tilde{k}_2^*$); Right: $\tau = h^2$ ($k_{max} > \tilde{k}_2^*$). Parameters: $\varepsilon = 2, \gamma = 1, L = 2h, h = 10^{-4}$.

Theorem 7 (Asymptotic results for three-point equi-oscillation). *The three-point equi-oscillation problem (34) between k_{min} , $\tilde{k}_1^* = B_1 h^{-\theta_1}$ and $\tilde{k}_2^* = B_2 h^{-\theta_2}$ for $0 < \theta_1 < \theta_2 \leq \frac{8}{5}$, is asymptotically solved for h small with $L = C_1 h$ by*

$$\begin{cases} p^* = 2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{4}} B_1^{\frac{1}{4}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}} h^{-\frac{\theta_1}{4}}, q^* = 2^{-\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{3}{4}} B_1^{\frac{1}{4}} B_2^{-\frac{1}{2}} a_{min}^{-\frac{1}{2}} h^{\frac{\theta_2}{4} - \frac{\theta_1}{4}} & \text{if } \theta_2 \leq \frac{8}{5}, \theta_1 < \frac{\theta_2}{2}, \\ p^* = \sqrt{2} a_{min} B_1^{-\frac{1}{4}} B_2^{\frac{1}{4}} h^{-\frac{\theta_2 - \theta_1}{4}}, q^* = \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{2}} (B_1 B_2)^{-\frac{1}{4}} h^{\frac{\theta_2 + \theta_1}{4}} & \text{if } \theta_2 \leq \frac{8}{5}, \theta_1 > \frac{\theta_2}{2}, \\ p^* = B_1^{\frac{1}{4}} B_2^{\frac{1}{4}} a_{min} \zeta_{min} h^{-\frac{\theta_1}{4}}, q^* = 2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{2}} B_1^{\frac{1}{4}} B_2^{-\frac{1}{4}} \zeta_{min} h^{\frac{3\theta_1}{4}}, & \text{if } \theta_2 < \frac{8}{5}, \theta_1 = \frac{\theta_2}{2}, \\ p^* = \tilde{C}_p (C_1 h)^{-\frac{1}{5}}, q^* = \tilde{C}_q (C_1 h)^{\frac{3}{5}}, & \text{if } \theta_2 = \frac{8}{5}, \theta_1 = \frac{4}{5}, \end{cases}$$

where $\zeta_{min} := (2^{\frac{1}{2}} B_1 + 2\varepsilon^{\frac{1}{2}} B_2^{\frac{1}{2}} a_{min})^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, $\tilde{C}_p := B_1^{\frac{1}{2}} (2 + B_2 C_1^{\frac{8}{5}} \tilde{C}_q - 2\varepsilon (B_1 B_2)^{\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{\frac{6}{5}} \tilde{C}_q^2) / (2\varepsilon B_2^{\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{\frac{2}{5}} \tilde{C}_q)$ and \tilde{C}_q is the unique positive root of the polynomial

$$\begin{aligned} P(\xi) = & 2\sqrt{2}\varepsilon C_1^{\frac{14}{5}} B_1^{\frac{3}{2}} B_2^{\frac{3}{2}} \xi^3 - 4\sqrt{2} C_1^{\frac{8}{5}} B_1 B_2 \xi - 4\sqrt{2} B_1 \\ & + C_1^{\frac{6}{5}} (4\sqrt{2}\varepsilon B_1^{\frac{3}{2}} B_2^{\frac{1}{2}} - \sqrt{2} C_1^2 B_1 B_2^2 + 8\varepsilon^{\frac{3}{2}} B_1^{\frac{1}{2}} B_2 a_{min}) \xi^2. \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Proof. We are still seeking a solution in an asymptotic sense. We make the ansatz $p^* = C_p L^{-\alpha}$ and $q^* = C_q L^\beta$, since numerical tests show that p^* tends to infinity and q^* tends to zero as $L \rightarrow 0$. Noting that $L = C_1 h$, we easily find asymptotic expansions of the three terms in (34),

$$\rho_M(k_{min}, L, p^*, q^*) = 1 - \frac{4a_{min}}{C_p} (C_1 h)^\alpha + O(h^{\min\{2\alpha, 1\}}), \quad (36)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_M(\tilde{k}_1^*, L, p^*, q^*) &= \tilde{\rho}_M(\tilde{k}_1^*, L, p^*, q^*) + O(L^{1 + \frac{\theta_1}{2} - \beta}) \\ &= 1 - \frac{2\sqrt{2}\varepsilon C_p}{\sqrt{B_1} C_1^\alpha} h^{\frac{\theta_1}{2} - \alpha} - 2\sqrt{2\varepsilon} B_1 C_q C_1^\beta h^{\beta - \frac{\theta_1}{2}} \\ &\quad + O(h^{\min\{1 - \frac{\theta_1}{2}, \theta_1 - 2\alpha, 2\beta - \theta_1\}}), \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho_M(\tilde{k}_2^*, L, p^*, q^*) &= \tilde{\rho}_M(\tilde{k}_2^*, L, p^*, q^*) + O(L^{1+\frac{\theta_2}{2}-\beta}) \\
&= 1 - \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon B_2 C_q C_1^\beta}} h^{\frac{\theta_2}{2}-\beta} - \frac{\sqrt{2B_2 C_1}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon}} h^{1-\frac{\theta_2}{2}} \\
&\quad + O(h^{\min\{\theta_2-2\beta, 1-\beta, 2-\theta_2\}}).
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

We need to consider the relationship between the exponents $\frac{\theta_1}{2} - \alpha$ and $\beta - \frac{\theta_1}{2}$, as well as $\frac{\theta_2}{2} - \beta$ and $1 - \frac{\theta_2}{2}$. Equalizing the exponents, i.e. solving

$$\alpha = \frac{\theta_1}{2} - \alpha = \beta - \frac{\theta_1}{2} = \frac{\theta_2}{2} - \beta = 1 - \frac{\theta_2}{2},$$

one finds $\alpha^* = \frac{1}{5}, \beta^* = \frac{3}{5}, \theta_1^* = \frac{4}{5}, \theta_2^* = \frac{8}{5}$. Then we have the following situations for $0 < \theta_1 < \theta_2 \leq \frac{8}{5}$:

1. $\theta_2 \leq \frac{8}{5}$ and $\theta_1 < \frac{\theta_2}{2}$. Equalizing the dominant terms, that is solving

$$\frac{4a_{min}}{C_p} (C_1 h)^\alpha = \frac{2\sqrt{2\varepsilon} C_p}{\sqrt{B_1} C_1^\alpha} h^{\frac{\theta_1}{2}-\alpha} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon B_2 C_q C_1^\beta}} h^{\frac{\theta_2}{2}-\beta},$$

we get $C_p = 2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{4}} B_1^{\frac{1}{4}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}} C_1^\alpha$, $C_q = 2^{-\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{3}{4}} B_1^{\frac{1}{4}} B_2^{-\frac{1}{2}} a_{min}^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{-\beta}$, and $\alpha = \frac{\theta_1}{4}$, $\beta = \frac{\theta_2}{2} - \frac{\theta_1}{4}$.

2. $\theta_2 \leq \frac{8}{5}$ and $\theta_1 > \frac{\theta_2}{2}$. Now, matching the exponents of the dominant terms

$$\frac{4a_{min}}{C_p} (C_1 h)^\alpha = 2\sqrt{2\varepsilon B_1} C_q C_1^\beta h^{\beta-\frac{\theta_1}{2}} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon B_2 C_q C_1^\beta}} h^{\frac{\theta_2}{2}-\beta},$$

we arrive at $C_p = \sqrt{2} a_{min} B_1^{-\frac{1}{4}} B_2^{\frac{1}{4}} C_1^\alpha$, $C_q = \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{2}} (B_1 B_2)^{-\frac{1}{4}} C_1^{-\beta}$, and $\alpha = \frac{\theta_2 - \theta_1}{4}$, $\beta = \frac{\theta_2 + \theta_1}{4}$.

3. $\theta_2 < \frac{8}{5}$ and $\theta_1 = \frac{\theta_2}{2}$. Now, via solving

$$\frac{4a_{min}}{C_p} (C_1 h)^\alpha = \frac{2\sqrt{2\varepsilon} C_p}{\sqrt{B_1} C_1^\alpha} h^{\frac{\theta_1}{2}-\alpha} + 2\sqrt{2\varepsilon B_1} C_q C_1^\beta h^{\beta-\frac{\theta_1}{2}} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon B_2 C_q C_1^\beta}} h^{\frac{\theta_2}{2}-\beta},$$

we obtain $\alpha = \frac{\theta_1}{4}, \beta = \frac{3\theta_1}{4}$, $C_p = B_1^{\frac{1}{4}} B_2^{\frac{1}{4}} a_{min} (2^{\frac{1}{2}} B_1 + 2\varepsilon^{\frac{1}{2}} B_2^{\frac{1}{2}} a_{min})^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_1^\alpha$ and $C_q = 2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{2}} B_1^{\frac{1}{4}} B_2^{-\frac{1}{4}} (2^{\frac{1}{2}} B_1 + 2\varepsilon^{\frac{1}{2}} B_2^{\frac{1}{2}} a_{min})^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{-\beta}$

4. $\theta_2 = \frac{8}{5}, \theta_1 = \frac{\theta_2}{2} = \frac{4}{5}$. In this case, we need to solve

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{4a_{min}}{C_p} (C_1 h)^\alpha &= \frac{2\sqrt{2\varepsilon} C_p}{\sqrt{B_1} C_1^\alpha} h^{\frac{\theta_1}{2}-\alpha} + 2\sqrt{2\varepsilon B_1} C_q C_1^\beta h^{\beta-\frac{\theta_1}{2}} \\
&= \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon B_2 C_q C_1^\beta}} h^{\frac{\theta_2}{2}-\beta} + \frac{\sqrt{2B_2 C_1}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon}} h^{1-\frac{\theta_2}{2}},
\end{aligned}$$

to obtain $\alpha = \frac{1}{5}, \beta = \frac{3}{5}, C_p = B_1^{\frac{1}{2}}(2 + B_2 C_1^{\frac{8}{5}} C_q - 2\varepsilon(B_1 B_2)^{\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{\frac{6}{5}} C_q^2)/(2\varepsilon B_2^{\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{\frac{2}{5}} C_q)$, C_q is the unique positive root of the polynomial (35). \square

Theorem 8 (Mixed transmission condition, overlapping case). *Let $L = C_1 h$ and $\tau = C_2 h^\delta$. The min-max problem (31) is asymptotically solved for h sufficiently small by*

$$\begin{cases} p^* = 2^{-\frac{1}{5}} a_{min}^{\frac{4}{5}} C_1^{-\frac{1}{5}} h^{-\frac{1}{5}}, \\ q^* = 2^{-\frac{2}{5}} \varepsilon^{-1} a_{min}^{-\frac{2}{5}} C_1^{\frac{3}{5}} h^{\frac{3}{5}}, \end{cases} \quad \text{if } \delta > \frac{8}{5}, \text{ or } \delta = \frac{8}{5} \text{ and } C_1 \geq C_m, \quad (39)$$

$$\begin{cases} p^* = C_{pq} C_1^{-1} h^{-\frac{1}{5}}, \\ q^* = C_{pq} \tilde{C}_{pq}^{-2} C_1^{-1} h^{\frac{3}{5}}, \end{cases} \quad \text{if } \delta = \frac{8}{5} \text{ and } C_1 < C_m, \quad (40)$$

$$\begin{cases} p^* = 2^{-\frac{1}{8}} \pi^{\frac{1}{8}} (\varepsilon C_2)^{-\frac{1}{8}} a_{min}^{\frac{3}{4}} h^{-\frac{6}{8}}, \\ q^* = 2^{-\frac{5}{8}} \pi^{-\frac{3}{8}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{5}{8}} C_2^{\frac{3}{8}} a_{min}^{-\frac{1}{4}} h^{\frac{3\delta}{8}}, \end{cases} \quad \text{if } 0 < \delta < \frac{8}{5}, \quad (41)$$

where $C_m = 2^{\frac{7}{8}} \pi^{-\frac{5}{8}} \varepsilon^{\frac{5}{8}} C_2^{\frac{5}{8}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{4}}$ and $C_{pq} := 2((2\pi\varepsilon C_2)^{\frac{1}{2}} a_{min} - C_2 \tilde{C}_{pq}^2) \pi^{-1}$ with \tilde{C}_{pq} being the unique positive root of polynomial

$$P(\zeta) = 4\sqrt{2}\varepsilon^{\frac{1}{2}} C_2^2 \zeta^4 - 16\varepsilon\pi^{\frac{1}{2}} C_2^{\frac{3}{2}} a_{min} \zeta^2 - \pi^2 C_1^2 a_{min} \zeta + 8\sqrt{2}\varepsilon^{\frac{3}{2}} \pi C_2 a_{min}^2.$$

The maximum of the corresponding convergence factor ρ_M has the following asymptotic expansion for h small

$$\begin{aligned} & \max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_M(k, L, p^*, q^*) \\ &= \begin{cases} 1 - 4 \cdot 2^{\frac{1}{5}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{5}} C_1^{\frac{1}{5}} h^{\frac{1}{5}} + O(h^{\frac{2}{5}}), & \text{if } \delta > \frac{8}{5}, \text{ or } \delta = \frac{8}{5} \text{ and } C_1 \geq C_m, \\ 1 - 4a_{min} C_{pq}^{-1} C_1 h^{\frac{1}{5}} + O(h^{\frac{2}{5}}), & \text{if } \delta = \frac{8}{5} \text{ and } C_1 < C_m, \\ 1 - 4 \cdot 2^{\frac{1}{8}} (\varepsilon C_2)^{\frac{1}{8}} \pi^{-\frac{1}{8}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{4}} h^{\frac{\delta}{8}} + O(h^{\frac{\delta}{4}}), & \text{if } 0 < \delta < \frac{8}{5}. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Similarly, we first, based on Theorem 7, determine the solutions p^* and q^* to the equi-oscillation problem in the admissible frequency domain \mathbb{K} . We make the ansatz: $p^* = C_p L^{-\alpha}, q^* = C_q L^\beta$. From Lemmas 1 and 4, we know that the location of the interior maximum of $\rho_M(k, L, p, q)$ in the asymptotic sense is

$$\bar{k}_1^* \sim \frac{p^*}{q^*} = C_p C_q^{-1} (C_1 h)^{-(\alpha+\beta)}, \quad \bar{k}_2^* \sim \frac{2}{L q^*} = 2 C_q^{-1} (C_1 h)^{-(1+\beta)}.$$

Note that, in a numerical calculation, an estimate for the maximum frequency is $k_{max} = \frac{\pi}{C_2 h^\delta}$. We thus need to consider the relationship between the maximum frequency k_{max} and \bar{k}_2^* .

If $k_{max} \geq \bar{k}_2^*$, which requires that $\delta > 1 + \beta$ or $\delta = 1 + \beta$ and $C_1 \geq (2C_2/(\pi C_q))^{\frac{1}{1+\beta}}$, we should equi-oscillate between k_{min}, \bar{k}_1^* and \bar{k}_2^* . Thus, let $\tilde{k}_1^* = \bar{k}_1^*, \tilde{k}_2^* = \bar{k}_2^*$, i.e.,

$\theta_1 = \alpha + \beta, \theta_2 = 1 + \beta$ in Theorem 7, equations (37), (38) now read

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_M(\bar{k}_1^*, L, p^*, q^*) &= \tilde{\rho}_M(\bar{k}_1^*, L, p^*, q^*) + O(L^{1+\frac{\alpha-\beta}{2}}) \\ &= 1 - 4\sqrt{2}\varepsilon^{\frac{1}{2}}(C_p C_q)^{\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{\frac{\beta-\alpha}{2}} h^{\frac{\beta-\alpha}{2}} + O(h^{\beta-\alpha}),\end{aligned}\quad (42)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_M(\bar{k}_2^*, L, p^*, q^*) &= \tilde{\rho}_M(\bar{k}_2^*, L, p^*, q^*) + O(L^{\frac{3+\beta}{2}}) \\ &= 1 - 4\varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_q^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{\frac{1-\beta}{2}} h^{\frac{1-\beta}{2}} + O(h^{1-\beta}),\end{aligned}\quad (43)$$

which lead to

$$\alpha^* = \frac{1}{5}, \beta^* = \frac{3}{5}, C_p = 2^{-\frac{1}{5}} a_{min}^{\frac{4}{5}}, C_q = 2^{-\frac{2}{5}} \varepsilon^{-1} a_{min}^{-\frac{2}{5}}. \quad (44)$$

It follows from these results that $k_{max} \geq \bar{k}_2^*$ is equivalent to $\delta > \frac{8}{5}$, or $\delta = \frac{8}{5}$ and $C_1 \geq 2^{\frac{7}{8}} \pi^{-\frac{5}{8}} \varepsilon^{\frac{5}{8}} C_2^{\frac{5}{8}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{4}} =: C_m$.

Then, when $\delta = \frac{8}{5}$ and $C_1 < C_m$, or $0 < \delta < \frac{8}{5}$, we have $k_{max} < \bar{k}_2^*$, and we should equi-oscillate between k_{min} , \bar{k}_1^* and k_{max} . Choosing $\tilde{k}_2^* = k_{max} = \frac{\pi}{C_2 h^\delta}$ in Theorem 7, one finds

$$\begin{cases} \alpha^* = \frac{1}{5}, C_p^* = C_{pq} C_1^{-\frac{4}{5}}, \\ \beta^* = \frac{3}{5}, C_q^* = C_{pq} \tilde{C}_{pq}^{-2} C_1^{-\frac{8}{5}}, \end{cases} \quad \text{if } \delta = \frac{8}{5} \text{ and } C_1 < C_m, \quad (45)$$

$$\begin{cases} \alpha^* = \frac{\delta}{8}, C_p^* = 2^{-\frac{1}{8}} \pi^{\frac{1}{8}} (\varepsilon C_2)^{-\frac{1}{8}} a_{min}^{\frac{3}{4}} C_1^{\frac{\delta}{8}}, \\ \beta^* = \frac{3\delta}{8}, C_q^* = 2^{-\frac{5}{8}} \pi^{-\frac{3}{8}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{5}{8}} C_2^{\frac{3}{8}} a_{min}^{-\frac{1}{4}} C_1^{-\frac{3\delta}{8}}, \end{cases} \quad \text{if } 0 < \delta < \frac{8}{5}, \quad (46)$$

where \tilde{C}_{pq} and C_{pq} are defined below (41).

Combining equations (44), (45) and (46), one finds the expression of the optimized parameters as shown in Theorem 8.

Inserting the asymptotic values of p^*, q^* given in (39), (40), (41), and $k = k_{min}$ into the convergence factor $\rho_M(k, L, p, q)$ and expanding for h small, we obtain the asymptotic expansions in Theorem 8.

We thus only need to show that p^*, q^* given in (39), (40) and (41) solve the min-max problem (31) asymptotically. Here we only show the detailed proof for the first case, $k_{max} > \bar{k}_2^*$ (c.f. the right plot in Fig. 1), and the other two cases (c.f. the left plot in Fig. 1) are similar. We first show that for $k_{min} < k < \underline{k}_1$ the convergence factor ρ_M is a decreasing function in k , where $\underline{k}_1 = \varepsilon(p^*)^2 \sim 2^{-\frac{2}{5}} \varepsilon a_{min}^{\frac{8}{5}} L^{\frac{2}{5}}$ is defined in Lemma 4. Again, we analyze using an asymptotic analysis as the following. Assume δ_k is a small increment of the frequency k , we then have by a direct calculation

$$\rho_M(k+\delta_k, 0, p^*, q^*) = \rho_M(k, 0, p^*, q^*)$$

$$+ \begin{cases} -\frac{\sqrt{2}(\sqrt{\varepsilon^2 C_k^2 + \gamma^2}(\varepsilon^2 C_k^2 + 2\gamma^2) - 2\gamma^3)}{C_p^*(\varepsilon^2 C_k^2 + \gamma^2)^{\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 C_k^2 + \gamma^2} - \gamma} L^{\frac{1}{5}} \delta_k + O(L^{\frac{2}{5}} \delta_k), & \text{if } \vartheta = 0, \\ -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon C_k C_p^*}} L^{\frac{1}{5} + \frac{\vartheta}{2}} \delta_k + O(L^{\frac{2}{5}} \delta_k), & \text{if } 0 < \vartheta < \frac{2}{5}, \\ \frac{\sqrt{2\varepsilon} C_p^*(C_k - \varepsilon(C_p^*)^2)}{\sqrt{C_k}(\sqrt{2\varepsilon C_k C_p^* + \varepsilon(C_p^*)^2} + C_k)^2} L^{\frac{2}{5}} \delta_k + O(L^{\frac{4}{5}} \delta_k) & \text{if } \vartheta = \frac{2}{5}, \\ \sqrt{2\varepsilon} C_p^* C_k^{-\frac{3}{2}} L^{\frac{3\vartheta}{2} - \frac{1}{5}} \delta_k + O(L^{\min\{2(\vartheta - \frac{1}{5}), \frac{\vartheta}{2} + \frac{3}{5}\}} \delta_k) & \text{if } \frac{2}{5} < \vartheta < \frac{4}{5}, \end{cases} \quad (47)$$

with $k = C_k L^{-\vartheta}$. Obviously, equation (47) shows that in asymptotic sense $\rho_M(k, 0, p^*, q^*)$ is monotonically decreasing in k for $k \in (k_{min}, \underline{k}_1)$. Thus, $\rho_M(k, L, p^*, q^*)$, as a product of two decreasing positive functions $\rho_M(k, 0, p^*, q^*)$ and $\rho_{cla}(k, L)$, must decrease in k for $k < \underline{k}_1$. As a consequence, k_{min} is a possible maximum point of $\rho_M(k, L, p^*, q^*)$ for h small enough, as well as the two interior maxima points $\bar{k}_{1,2}^*$ found in Lemma 4.

We now need to show that (p, q) differs from (p^*, q^*) leading to a convergence factor ρ_M that could be further improved. To this end, let $p = C_p L^{-\alpha}$, $q = C_q L^\beta$ and $p^* = C_p L^{-\alpha^*}$, $q^* = C_q L^{\beta^*}$, where $\alpha^* = \frac{1}{5}$, $\beta^* = \frac{3}{5}$, as shown in (39). We now need to show that if $(p, q) \neq (p^*, q^*)$, then there exists a k^* such that for $h > 0$ small enough

$$\rho_M(k^*, L, p, q) > \max_k \rho_M(k, L, p^*, q^*) = \rho_M(k_{min}, L, p^*, q^*),$$

where the search for k^* can be steered by tracking how ρ_M evolves with p and q , as illustrated in Fig. 1. Here, we again employ the technique proposed by Gander and Xu [24, 25]. We first show that if $(\alpha, \beta) \neq (\alpha^*, \beta^*)$, then the asymptotic order of the resulting OSWR method will be enlarged. To do this, it is sufficient to treat the following cases:

(a) $\alpha > \alpha^*, \beta > -\alpha$. At $k^* = k_{min}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_M(k^*, L, p, q) &= 1 - \frac{4a_{min} C_1^\alpha h^\alpha}{C_p} - \frac{4k_{min} b_{min} C_q}{C_p^2} C_1^{\beta+2\alpha} h^{\beta+2\alpha} \\ &\quad - 2a_{min} C_1 h + o(h^{\min\{\alpha, \beta+2\alpha, 1\}}). \end{aligned}$$

(b) $\alpha > \alpha^*, \beta = -\alpha$. At $k^* = k_{min}$, we have

$$\rho_M(k^*, L, p, q) = 1 - 2a_{min} C_1 h - \frac{4a_{min} C_p + 4k_{min} b_{min} C_q}{C_p^2 + k_{min}^2 C_q^2} C_1^\alpha h^\alpha + o(h^{\min\{\alpha, 1\}}).$$

(c) $\alpha > \alpha^*, \beta < -\alpha$. At $k^* = k_{min}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_M(k^*, L, p, q) &= 1 - \frac{4b_{min}}{k_{min} C_q} (C_1 h)^{-\beta} - \frac{4a_{min} C_p}{k_{min}^2 C_q^2} (C_1 h)^{-(2\beta+\alpha)} \\ &\quad - 2a_{min} C_1 h + o(h^{\min\{-\beta, -(2\beta+\alpha), 1\}}). \end{aligned}$$

- (d) $\alpha = \alpha^*, \beta > \beta^*$. Here we have to treat two cases: If $\beta < 1$, for $k^* = C_k L^{-(\alpha+\beta)}$, we have

$$\rho_M(k^*, L, p, q) = 1 - \frac{2\sqrt{2\varepsilon}(C_q C_k + C_p)}{\sqrt{C_k}} (C_1 h)^{\frac{\beta-\alpha}{2}} + o(h^{\frac{\beta-\alpha}{2}}).$$

If $\beta \geq 1$, we take $k^* = C_k L^{-1}$ to obtain

$$\rho_M(k^*, L, p, q) = 1 - \frac{2\sqrt{2\varepsilon}C_p}{\sqrt{C_k}} (C_1 h)^{\frac{3}{10}} + o(h^{\frac{3}{10}}).$$

- (e) $\alpha \leq \alpha^*, \beta < \beta^*$. At $k^* = C_k L^{-(1+\beta)}$, we have

$$\rho_M(k^*, L, p, q) = 1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}(2 + C_k C_q)}{\sqrt{\varepsilon C_k C_q}} (C_1 h)^{\frac{1-\beta}{2}} + O(h^{\frac{1-\beta}{2}}).$$

- (f) $\alpha < \alpha^*, \beta > \beta^*$. At $k^* = C_k L^{-\frac{4}{5}}$, it holds

$$\rho_M(k^*, L, p, q) = 1 - \frac{2\sqrt{2\varepsilon}C_p}{\sqrt{C_k}} (C_1 h)^{\frac{2}{5}-\alpha} - 2\sqrt{2\varepsilon C_k C_q} (C_1 h)^{\beta-\frac{2}{5}} + o(h^{\min\{\frac{2}{5}-\alpha, \beta-\frac{2}{5}, \frac{3}{5}\}}).$$

- (g) $\alpha < \alpha^*, \beta = \beta^*$. At $k^* = C_k L^{-(\alpha+\beta)}$, we get

$$\rho_M(k^*, L, p, q) = 1 - \frac{2\sqrt{2\varepsilon}}{\sqrt{C_k}} (C_p + C_k C_q) (C_1 h)^{\frac{\beta-\alpha}{2}} + o(h^{\frac{\beta-\alpha}{2}}).$$

We therefore see that in each case above, at the given k^* , the convergence factor $\rho_M(k^*, L, p, q)$ behaves asymptotically like $1 - Ch^\delta$ with $\delta > \frac{1}{5}$.

It remains thus to consider the case $\alpha = \alpha^*$ and $\beta = \beta^*$ but $(C_p, C_q) \neq (C_p^*, C_q^*)$. From (36) we see $\rho_M(k_{min}, L, p, q) > \rho_M(k_{min}, L, p^*, q^*)$ asymptotically if $C_p > C_p^*$. From (43) we see $\rho_M(\bar{k}_2, L, p, q) > \rho_M(\bar{k}_2, L, p^*, q^*)$ if $C_q > C_q^*$, and from (42) we conclude that $\rho_M(\bar{k}_1, L, p, q) > \rho_M(\bar{k}_1, L, p^*, q^*)$ if $C_p < C_p^*$ or $C_q < C_q^*$, which concludes the proof. \square

For the non-overlapping case, the mixed transmission condition can also be optimized, the results are shown below.

Theorem 9 (Mixed transmission condition, non-overlapping case). *When there is no overlap, i.e. $L = 0$, the min-max problem (31) is solved by the parameters*

$$p^* = (2\varepsilon)^{-\frac{1}{8}} a_{min}^{\frac{3}{4}} k_{max}^{\frac{1}{8}}, \quad q^* = (2\varepsilon)^{-\frac{5}{8}} a_{min}^{-\frac{1}{4}} k_{max}^{-\frac{3}{8}}$$

in an asymptotic sense of k_{max} large, which leads the convergence factor to the following asymptotic estimate

$$\max_{k \geq k_{min}} \rho_M(k, 0, p^*, q^*) = 1 - 4 \cdot (2\varepsilon)^{\frac{1}{8}} a_{min}^{\frac{1}{4}} k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{8}} + O(k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}}).$$

Proof. The proof is very similar to that for Theorems 3 and 8. \square

Remark 4. Comparing the results from Theorem 8 with those from Theorem 9, again we find that if $\delta < \frac{8}{5}$, an overlap cannot improve the performance of the OSWR algorithm with mixed transmission conditions. The situation is quite similar to the results of Remarks 2 and 3. Bennequin, Gander and Halpern [7] have revealed similar phenomena for the advection reaction diffusion problems.

Table 1: Convergence factor estimates for the OSWR algorithm (6) with Robin, characteristic and mixed transmission conditions, respectively, for $\tau = C_2 h^\delta$.

Method		$\max \rho$
with overlap $L = C_1 h$	Robin	$1 - 4a_{\min}^{\frac{1}{3}} C_1^{\frac{1}{3}} h^{\frac{1}{3}} + O(h^{\frac{2}{3}}), \quad \text{if } \delta > \frac{4}{3}$
		$1 - 4a_{\min}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\varepsilon C_2}{2\pi}\right)^{\frac{1}{4}} h^{\frac{\delta}{4}} + O(h^{\frac{\delta}{2}}), \quad \text{if } \delta < \frac{4}{3}$
	Char.	$1 - 2^{\frac{4}{3}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{3}} \varsigma_{\min}^{\frac{1}{3}} C_1^{\frac{1}{3}} h^{\frac{1}{3}} + O(h^{\frac{2}{3}}), \quad \text{if } \delta > \frac{4}{3}$
		$1 - 2^{\frac{3}{4}} (\varepsilon \pi)^{-\frac{1}{4}} C_2^{\frac{1}{4}} \varsigma_{\min}^{\frac{1}{2}} h^{\frac{\delta}{4}} + O(h^{\frac{\delta}{2}}), \quad \text{if } \delta < \frac{4}{3}$
	Mixed	$1 - 4 \cdot 2^{\frac{1}{5}} a_{\min}^{\frac{1}{5}} C_1^{\frac{1}{5}} h^{\frac{1}{5}} + O(h^{\frac{2}{5}}), \quad \text{if } \delta > \frac{8}{5}$
		$1 - 4 \cdot 2^{\frac{1}{8}} (\varepsilon C_2)^{\frac{1}{8}} \pi^{-\frac{1}{8}} a_{\min}^{\frac{1}{4}} h^{\frac{\delta}{8}} + O(h^{\frac{\delta}{4}}), \quad \text{if } 0 < \delta < \frac{8}{5}$
without overlap $L = 0$	Robin	$1 - 4 \cdot 2^{-\frac{1}{4}} \varepsilon^{\frac{1}{4}} a_{\min}^{\frac{1}{2}} k_{\max}^{-\frac{1}{4}} + O(k_{\max}^{-\frac{1}{2}})$
	Char.	$1 - 2^{\frac{3}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{4}} \varsigma_{\min}^{\frac{1}{2}} k_{\max}^{-\frac{1}{4}} + O(k_{\max}^{-\frac{1}{2}})$
	Mixed	$1 - 4 \cdot (2\varepsilon)^{\frac{1}{8}} a_{\min}^{\frac{1}{4}} k_{\max}^{-\frac{1}{8}} + O(k_{\max}^{-\frac{1}{4}})$

Remark 5. We summarize in Table 1 the asymptotic convergence factor estimates of the OSWR algorithm (6) under different transmission conditions, with particular attention to the case of small ε . As $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, the following asymptotic expansions hold:

$$a_{\min} = 2k_{\min}^2 \gamma^{-\frac{3}{2}} \varepsilon + O(\varepsilon^3),$$

$$\varsigma_{\min} = 4\gamma^{\frac{1}{2}} + O(\varepsilon^2).$$

Using these expansions, we observe that for a fixed mesh size h (or equivalently, a fixed time step τ), only the characteristic transmission condition maintains superior performance when ε is small—regardless of overlap. This advantage stems from the fact that a small ε otherwise leads to a small convergence factor. In contrast, both Robin and mixed transmission conditions are negatively impacted by small ε , which increases their respective convergence factors. The three-point equi-oscillation behavior under mixed transmission conditions is illustrated in Fig. 2 for $\varepsilon = 0.01$. A comparison with Fig. 1 reveals that a small ε necessitates a considerably larger frequency range to achieve equi-oscillation, thereby making the choice of a practical time step infeasible in actual computations. We comment here also that when $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, though the viscoelastic equation (1) degenerates to the standard wave equation, all transmission conditions considered above cannot recover the optimal transmission condition for the wave equation developed in [19]. A similar analysis shows that for large ε , the Robin

transmission condition performs better than the characteristic condition, although both converge at the same asymptotic order. Furthermore, the mixed transmission condition performs the best among the three, as it achieves the highest asymptotic order of convergence.

Fig. 2: Illustration of the equi-oscillation property for weak damping. Left: $\tau = h$ ($k_{max} < \tilde{k}_2^*$); Right: $\tau = h^2$ ($k_{max} > \tilde{k}_2^*$). Parameters: $\varepsilon = 0.01, \gamma = 1, L = 2h, h = 10^{-12}$.

6 Numerical experiments

In this section, we would like to present several numerical examples to illustrate our theoretical results. We consider the viscoelastic equation (1) with $\Omega = (-1, 1)$, the initial conditions $u(x, 0) = \sin(2\pi x)$, $\partial_t u(x, 0) = -\sin(2\pi x)$ and the source function $f(x, t) = (1 - 4\varepsilon\pi^2 + 4\gamma\pi^2) \sin(2\pi x)e^{-t}$. The exact solution reads $u(x, t) = \sin(2\pi x)e^{-t}$. Without loss of generality, we set the parameter $\gamma = 1$ and the final time $T = 1$. We partition the domain Ω into two subdomains: $\Omega_1 = (-1, l)$ and $\Omega_2 = (-l, 1)$, where l is an integer multiple of the spatial step size h . Unless otherwise specified, we set $l = h$, resulting in an overlap region of length $L = 2h$. The OSWR algorithm (6) is applied to solve equation (1) with the above setting, using the following interface scheme

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_x u_1^n(l, t) + (p + q\partial_t)u_1^n(l, t) &= g_1^n, \quad t \in (0, T], \\ -\partial_x u_2^n(-l, t) + (p + q\partial_t)u_2^n(-l, t) &= g_2^n, \quad t \in (0, T], \end{aligned}$$

where g_1^n and g_2^n are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} g_1^n &= \partial_x u_2^{n-1}(l, t) + (p + q\partial_t)u_2^{n-1}(l, t), \\ g_2^n &= -\partial_x u_1^{n-1}(-l, t) + (p + q\partial_t)u_1^{n-1}(-l, t), \end{aligned}$$

which can be updated when there is no overlap, i.e. $l = 0$, as

$$\begin{aligned} g_1^n &= -g_2^{n-1} + 2(p + q\partial_t)u_2^{n-1}, \\ g_2^n &= -g_1^{n-1} + 2(p + q\partial_t)u_1^{n-1}, \end{aligned}$$

avoiding explicitly formulating the Neumann information $\partial_x u_2^{n-1}(0, t)$ and $\partial_x u_1^{n-1}(0, t)$ from calculated data u_2^{n-1} and u_1^{n-1} . The centered finite difference method is used for spatial discretization, while for temporal discretization, we use the Crank-Nicolson scheme. All experiments are implemented using MATLAB_R2016b, with a random initial guess $g_i^0 (i = 1, 2)$ and stop when the maximum difference between two successive iterations satisfies the stopping criterion

$$\max\{\|g_1^n - g_1^{n-1}\|_\infty, \|g_2^n - g_2^{n-1}\|_\infty\} < tol,$$

where tol is a given tolerance.

6.1 Convergence behavior

For a general test on the convergence behavior of SWR algorithms with different transmission conditions, we set $\varepsilon = 2$ in our example. In order to compare the classical SWR algorithm with the Dirichlet transmission condition, which does not converge without overlap, we only show the numerical experimental results of the algorithm with overlap.

Denote by $e_i^n = u_i^n - u_h$ the error over all space-time grids in Ω_i , $i = 1, 2$, where u_h is the exact solution evaluated at the grid points. In Fig. 3, we show the curve of the maximum error $\|e^n\|_\infty = \max\{\|e_1^n\|_\infty, \|e_2^n\|_\infty\}$ decreasing with the number of iterations, where $\tau = h$ (according to the theoretical results, the overlap does not help convergence) on the left and $\tau = h^2$ (the overlap does help) on the right, with

Fig. 3: Maximum error decay of the classical SWR algorithm and the OSWR algorithm with optimized transmission conditions: Robin, characteristic and mixed. Left: $\tau = O(h)$; Right: $\tau = O(h^2)$.

$h = 0.01$. It clearly shows that the OSWR converges much faster than the classical SWR, for all three transmission conditions: Robin, characteristic and mixed.

Now, we investigate how well the asymptotic analysis predicts the optimized parameters to be used in the numerical setting. To this end, for the Robin transmission condition, we vary the parameter p and count for each value of p the number of iterations to reach the stopping criterion with tolerance $tol = 10^{-3}$, and do the same for the other transmission conditions. The results are shown in Fig. 4a with $\tau = h = 0.01$, where the predicted parameters in Theorems 2, 5, and 8 are indicated by a red star. From these plots, it can be observed that our theoretical predictions are very close to the numerically optimal parameters. In addition, it is also of interest to check if these predictions are sensitive to the tolerance specified in the stopping criterion. We thus redo the above experiment, for a much smaller tolerance $tol = 10^{-6}$ with $\tau = h = 0.01$, and plot the results in Fig. 4b. One finds that the tolerance value only slightly affects the prediction accuracy, as evidenced by a comparison with Fig. 4a. A careful check on the error curve shows that this minor difference is due to the preset tolerance level: after reaching the discretization error, the algorithm uses more iterations to meet the stopping criterion, as shown in Fig. 5. To sum up, the asymptotic analysis predicts the optimal parameters in practice very well.

(a) Parameters: $\varepsilon = 2, \tau = h = 0.01, tol = 10^{-3}$

(b) Parameters: $\varepsilon = 2, \tau = h = 0.01, tol = 10^{-6}$

Fig. 4: Optimized parameter (*) found by asymptotic analysis, compared with the performance of other parameter values. Left: Robin; Middle: Characteristic; Right: Mixed.

Fig. 5: Maximum error decay of the OSWR algorithm with Robin condition. Parameter setting is the same as Fig. 4. $p = 4.78$ is the numerically optimal parameter.

We then switch to illustrate the asymptotic analysis in Theorems 2, 5, and 8 by performing two sets of experiments. The problem parameters are defined as previously, and now we start with a coarser grid. The space mesh size is taken as $h = 1/10, 1/20, 1/40, 1/80, 1/160, 1/320$ and the time step size is $\tau = h$ or $\tau = h^2$. We run the classical SWR and OSWR with Robin, characteristic and mixed transmission conditions until the stopping criterion $tol = 10^{-3}$ is reached, and count the number of iterations. For $\tau = h$, we know from (22) that the convergence factor of the classical SWR behaves like $1 - O(h)$; While for OSWR with Robin and characteristic conditions, it behaves like $1 - O(h^{\frac{1}{4}})$, as described in Theorem 2 and Theorem 5, respectively; The OSWR with mixed transmission conditions behave like $1 - O(h^{\frac{1}{8}})$, see Theorem 8. For $\tau = h^2$, the convergence factors of the OSWR with Robin, characteristic and mixed transmission conditions behave like $1 - O(h^{\frac{1}{3}})$, $1 - O(h^{\frac{1}{3}})$ and $1 - O(h^{\frac{1}{5}})$ respectively, while the classical SWR remains unchanged, $1 - O(h)$. These results are well justified in Fig. 6. To sum up, the OSWR algorithm exhibits varying asymptotic convergence rates under identical overlap conditions, contingent upon the temporal discretization, as anticipated.

We next investigate the effect of the overlap size L on the convergence behavior of the algorithm (6). The experiment is conducted with time step size $\tau = h$ and $\tau = h^2$, respectively, with spatial mesh size $h = 0.01$ and convergence tolerance $tol = 10^{-3}$. The number of iterations required by the OSWR algorithm (6) with Robin, characteristic, and mixed transmission conditions under varying overlap sizes $L = 0, 2h, 4h, 8h$ are reported in Table 2. The results show that for all three transmission conditions, the overlap accelerates the convergence for $\tau = h^2$: the bigger the overlap, the faster the algorithm converges; however, for $\tau = h$, the overlap can almost not accelerate the convergence. This observation well conforms to the results in Remarks 2, 3 and 4.

Finally, we examine how the Fourier analysis-based convergence factor is related to the convergence behavior of the algorithm in practice. Note that the error of the OSWR algorithm satisfies $e_i^{2n} = \rho^n e_i^0, i = 1, 2$, where e_i^0 denotes the initial error, c.f.

Fig. 6: The asymptotic behavior as the spatial grid is refined with the overlap $L = 2h$, together with the predicted rates from analysis, both for the classical SWR and OSWR with Robin, characteristic, and mixed transmission conditions. Left: $\tau = h$; Right: $\tau = h^2$.

Table 2: For varying overlap L and $h = 0.01$, the number of iterations required by the OSWR algorithm with Robin, characteristic, and mixed transmission conditions converging to the tolerance $tol = 10^{-3}$, for $\tau = h$ and $\tau = h^2$ (in brackets).

L	0	$2h$	$4h$	$8h$
Robin	13[27]	13[13]	12[10]	12[8]
Char.	13[26]	13[13]	13[10]	12[8]
Mixed	7[10]	7[7]	7[6]	6[5]

(7). To suppress the relative error to be less than a given tolerance, say,

$$\max\left\{\frac{\|e_1^n\|_\infty}{\|e_1^0\|_\infty}, \frac{\|e_2^n\|_\infty}{\|e_2^0\|_\infty}\right\} < tol,$$

it will require $N_{pred} := \lceil \frac{2 \ln(tol)}{\ln(\max \rho)} \rceil$ iterations, where $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ is the ceiling function. Table 3 compares the actual number of iterations required by the OSWR algorithm (6) with the predicted number, based on the respective convergence factors, for a tolerance of $tol = 10^{-3}$. The results demonstrate that for all three transmission conditions, the prediction derived from the convergence factors provides an upper bound on the required number of iterations. This confirms that the min-max approach for the convergence factors only yields a worst-case bound that is not very sharp, and that in practice, the method can be more efficient than anticipated.

Table 3: Number of iterations (N_{iter}) required by the OSWR algorithm (6) with Robin, characteristic, and mixed transmission conditions compared with their predictions by the convergence factors (N_{pred}). Parameters: $\tau = h$, $tol = 10^{-3}$.

h	Robin			Char.			Mixed		
	$\max \rho_R$	N_{pred}	N_{iter}	$\max \rho_C$	N_{pred}	N_{iter}	$\max \rho_M$	N_{pred}	N_{iter}
$\frac{1}{40}$	0.3432	13	8	0.2996	12	8	0.1211	7	5
$\frac{1}{80}$	0.4087	16	10	0.3685	14	9	0.1505	8	5
$\frac{1}{160}$	0.4720	19	11	0.4349	17	11	0.1769	8	5
$\frac{1}{320}$	0.5317	22	13	0.4980	20	13	0.2016	9	6
$\frac{1}{640}$	0.5874	26	15	0.5571	24	15	0.2255	10	6
$\frac{1}{1280}$	0.6388	31	18	0.6117	29	17	0.2498	10	6

6.2 The effect of damping coefficient ε

In this section, we investigate the robustness of various transmission conditions to the damping coefficient ε . Using the same exact solution as in Sect. 6.1, we vary the value of the damping coefficient ε and see how the OSWR algorithm responds. We note that when ε approaches 0, the viscoelastic equation (1) will degenerate into a typical wave equation, on which Gander et al. [19] showed that the best transmission condition is the characteristic condition with parameter $q = 1/\sqrt{\gamma}$. In the experiment, we also examine the convergence effect of this parameter for comparison. To see the effect of the damping coefficient ε more clearly, we show the number of iterations as a function of ε in the left plot of Fig. 7, with $tol=10^{-3}$ and $\tau = h = 0.01$. Here, a fixed tolerance for varying ε is still good, since the solutions do not vary with ε , and the maximum norm is applied. It is clear that for very small ε , the characteristic transmission condition outperforms the Robin and mixed, conforming well with the analysis from Remark 5, though it remains slightly inferior to the parameter selection $q = 1/\sqrt{\gamma}$ determined directly by the wave equation (we call it wave transmission condition in the rest of this paper). For not very small ε , say for example, $0.1 < \varepsilon < 10$, the Robin and characteristic transmission conditions perform very similarly, but neither converges faster than the mixed transmission condition, which is consistent with our asymptotic analysis results. For even strong damping, say $\varepsilon > 10$, we find that for all transmission conditions considered in this paper the performance deteriorates. However, the mixed transmission condition is still the best, as indicated by Remark 5. Among the transmission conditions using only one parameter, Robin performs the best, which is again consistent with Remark 5. As a comparison, we repeat this experiment with a smaller mesh size, $\tau = h = 0.002$, and show the results in the right plot of Fig. 7. The results show that each curve has a similar trend as ε varies, compared with the case $\tau = h = 0.01$. However, for small ε , both the Robin and mixed

transmission conditions require significantly more iterations to converge. This observation is consistent with the asymptotic estimates in Table 1, which indicate that for small ε , reducing the mesh size h drives the convergence factors closer to 1. However, the mixed transmission condition holds promise as it encompasses the characteristic condition—known for its excellent performance—as a special case. The key to realizing its potential under weak damping lies in developing a new strategy for determining the optimal parameter.

Fig. 7: The number of iterations as a function of ε with $L = 2h, \tau = h, tol = 10^{-3}$. Left: $h = 0.01$; Right: $h = 0.002$.

To evaluate the predictive capability of asymptotic analysis for determining optimal parameters in the case of weak damping, we choose $\varepsilon = 0.01$. Following the experimental methodology used for generating Fig. 4, we perform the numerical experiments with $tol = 10^{-3}$, and two step sizes: $\tau = h = 0.01$ and $\tau = h = 0.002$. The results presented in Fig. 8 show that, for both the Robin and characteristic conditions, a very fine mesh is required to achieve an accurate prediction based on asymptotic analysis. However, it appears that for the characteristic condition, the damping coefficient ε and the mesh size h must be related in some way to achieve an accurate prediction.

6.3 Finite element discretization

To evaluate the impact of spatio-temporal discretizations on the performance of the OSWR algorithm (6), we discretize space using linear finite elements and time using the backward Euler scheme. We then reproduce the two experiments from subsection 6.1 with this new discretization while keeping all parameter settings unchanged. The results, presented in Figures 9 and 10, are largely consistent with those in Figures 4 and 6, confirming that our analysis is only marginally affected by the choice of discretization.

(a) Parameters: $\varepsilon = 0.01, \tau = h, h = 0.01, tol = 10^{-3}$

(b) Parameters: $\varepsilon = 0.01, \tau = h, h = 0.002, tol = 10^{-3}$

Fig. 8: Optimized parameter (*) found by asymptotic analysis, compared with the performance of other parameter values. Left: Robin; Middle: Characteristic; Right: Mixed.

Fig. 9: Optimized parameter (*) found by asymptotic analysis, compared with the performance of other parameter values when the viscoelastic equation is discretized by the finite element method. Left: Robin; Middle: Characteristic; Right: Mixed. Parameters: $\varepsilon = 2, \tau = h, h = 0.01, tol = 10^{-3}$.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, the OSWR algorithm is developed for solving the viscoelastic equation. With the aid of an asymptotically accurate approximation of the convergence factor, we derive closed-form asymptotic formulas for Robin, characteristic and mixed transmission conditions, and obtain the corresponding convergence rate estimate, for both overlapping and non-overlapping cases. The theoretical results reveal for the first time that the efficacy of subdomain overlap in accelerating the convergence of the

Fig. 10: When discretized by the finite element method, the asymptotic behavior as the spatial grid is refined with the overlap $L = 2h$, together with the predicted rates from analysis, both for the classical SWR and OSWR with Robin, characteristic, and mixed transmission conditions. Left: $\tau = h$; Right: $\tau = h^2$.

OSWR algorithm for the viscoelastic wave equation is fundamentally governed by the value of δ in $\tau = C_2 h^\delta$, i.e., the scaling relationship between temporal and spatial discretizations. Similar results have been reported for parabolic problems in [17, 7]. More importantly, though Robin and characteristic transmission conditions behave asymptotically the same, they are affected by the viscoelastic coefficient ε differently: the characteristic transmission condition performs quite well across all values of ε , while the Robin condition outperforms the characteristic one only for very large ε . Furthermore, although the mixed transmission condition is theoretically expected to perform well under all circumstances, numerical results reveal performance degradation in weak damping scenarios when the grid is not sufficiently refined. It is therefore promising to investigate the optimal parameters for the mixed transmission condition under weak damping for mesh sizes commonly encountered in practice.

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Appendix

A: Proof of Theorem 4

Proof. Using the ansatz $q^* = C_q L^\alpha$ with $L = C_1 h$ and asymptotically expanding both sides of (26) for h small, we find

$$1 - \frac{4k_{min}b_{min}}{a_{min}^2 + b_{min}^2} C_q C_1^\alpha h^\alpha + \dots = 1 - \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon C} C_q} C_1^{-\alpha} h^{\frac{\theta}{2} - \alpha} - \sqrt{\frac{2C}{\varepsilon}} C_1 h^{1 - \frac{\theta}{2}} + \dots \quad (48)$$

Using the same technique as in the proof of Theorem 1, we obtain

$$\frac{4k_{min}b_{min}}{a_{min}^2 + b_{min}^2} C_q C_1^\alpha h^\alpha = \begin{cases} \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon C} C_q} C_1^{-\alpha} h^{\frac{\theta}{2} - \alpha}, & \text{if } 0 < \theta < \frac{4}{3}, \\ \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\varepsilon C} C_q} C_1^{-\alpha} h^{\frac{\theta}{2} - \alpha} + \sqrt{\frac{2C}{\varepsilon}} C_1 h^{1 - \frac{\theta}{2}}, & \text{if } \theta = \frac{4}{3}, \\ \sqrt{\frac{2C}{\varepsilon}} C_1 h^{1 - \frac{\theta}{2}} & \text{if } \frac{4}{3} < \theta < 2, \end{cases}$$

which leads to the solution

$$\begin{cases} \alpha^* = \frac{\theta}{4}, C_q^* = 2^{\frac{3}{4}} (\varepsilon C)^{-\frac{1}{4}} C_1^{-\frac{\theta}{4}} \varsigma_{min}^{-\frac{1}{2}}, & \text{if } 0 < \theta < \frac{4}{3}, \\ \alpha^* = \frac{1}{3}, C_q^* = (2\varepsilon C)^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{-\frac{1}{3}} \varsigma_{min}^{-1} (\sqrt{C^2 C_1^2 + 2^{\frac{3}{2}} (\varepsilon C)^{\frac{1}{2}} \varsigma_{min} + C C_1}), & \text{if } \theta = \frac{4}{3}, \\ \alpha^* = 1 - \frac{\theta}{2}, C_q^* = 2^{\frac{1}{2}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{2}} C^{\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{\frac{\theta}{2}} \varsigma_{min}^{-1}, & \text{if } \frac{4}{3} < \theta < 2, \end{cases}$$

where $\varsigma_{min} = 4k_{min}b_{min}/(a_{min}^2 + b_{min}^2)$. Thus, the parameter q^* in (27) is announced. \square

B: Proof of Theorem 5

Proof. The proof can also be divided into four steps.

As the first step, we, based on Theorem 4, determine the solution q^* to the equi-oscillation problem in the admissible frequency domain \mathbb{K} . We assume again $q^* = C_q L^\alpha$. From Lemmas 1 and 3, we know that the location of the unique interior maximum of $\rho_C(k, L, q)$ in the asymptotic sense is

$$\bar{k}^* := \bar{k}(q^*) = \frac{\varepsilon q^* + \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 (q^*)^2 - 2\varepsilon q^* L - L^2}}{\varepsilon (q^*)^2 L} = \frac{2}{C_q} (C_1 h)^{-(1+\alpha)} + O(h^{-2\alpha}),$$

where we have used the assumption $L = C_1 h$. Similarly to the proof of Theorem 2, we need to consider the relationship between the maximum frequency $k_{max} = \frac{\pi}{C_2 h^\delta}$ and \bar{k}^* .

If $k_{max} \geq \bar{k}^*$, which occurs when $\delta > 1 + \alpha$, or when $\delta = 1 + \alpha$ and $C_1 \geq (2C_2/(\pi C_q))^{1/(1+\alpha)}$, we should equi-oscillate between k_{min} and \bar{k}^* . Thus, let $\tilde{k}^* = \bar{k}^* = \frac{2}{C_q C_1} h^{-(1+\alpha)} + O(h^{-2\alpha})$, i.e., $\theta = 1 + \alpha$, $C = \frac{2}{C_q C_1^{1+\alpha}}$ in Theorem 4, equation (48) now reads

$$1 - \varsigma_{min} C_q C_1^\alpha h^\alpha + \dots = 1 - \frac{4}{\sqrt{\varepsilon C_q}} C_1^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\alpha}{2}} h^{\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\alpha}{2}} + \dots,$$

which leads to

$$\alpha^* = \frac{1}{3}, C_q^* = 2^{\frac{4}{3}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{3}} \varsigma_{min}^{-\frac{2}{3}}. \quad (49)$$

Using these results, one finds that $k_{max} \geq \bar{k}^*$ is equivalent to $\delta > \frac{4}{3}$, or $\delta = \frac{4}{3}$ and $C_1 \geq 2^{-\frac{1}{4}} (C_2/\pi)^{\frac{3}{4}} \varepsilon^{\frac{1}{4}} \varsigma_{min}^{\frac{1}{2}} =: C_c$.

Then, when $\delta < \frac{4}{3}$, or $\delta = \frac{4}{3}$ and $C_1 < C_c$, which means $k_{max} < \bar{k}^*$, thus we need to equi-oscillate between k_{min} and k_{max} . Choosing $\tilde{k}^* = k_{max} = \frac{\pi}{C_2 h^\delta}$ in Theorem 4, one finds

$$\begin{cases} \alpha^* = \frac{1}{3}, C_q^* = \tilde{C}_q, & \text{if } \delta = \frac{4}{3} \text{ and } C_1 < C_c, \\ \alpha^* = \frac{\delta}{4}, C_q^* = 2^{\frac{3}{4}} (\varepsilon \pi)^{-\frac{1}{4}} C_2^{\frac{1}{4}} C_1^{-\frac{\delta}{4}} \varsigma_{min}^{-\frac{1}{2}}, & \text{if } \delta < \frac{4}{3}, \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

where $\tilde{C}_q = (2\varepsilon\pi C_2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} C_1^{-\frac{1}{3}} \varsigma_{min}^{-1} (\sqrt{\pi^2 C_1^2 + (2C_2)^{\frac{3}{2}} (\varepsilon\pi)^{\frac{1}{2}} \varsigma_{min} + \pi C_1})$. By combining equations (49) and (50), we obtain the expression for the optimized parameter in (29).

In the second step, we show that $\rho_C(k, h, q^*)$ attains its maximum asymptotically at either $k = k_{min}$ or \bar{k}^* . Using the same proof as Theorem 2, we know that k_{min} and \bar{k}^* are the only two maximum points of $\rho_C(k, h, q^*)$ for $k \in \mathbb{K}$.

In the third step, we show that q^* in (29) solves the min-max problem (25) in an asymptotic sense. To this end, we only need to show that any parameters asymptotically different from q^* would yield a maximum value of ρ_C greater than $\rho_C(k_{min}, L, q^*)$. For brevity, we show only the detailed proof for the first case, i.e., $k_{max} > \bar{k}^*$, and the other two cases can be obtained in a similar way. Assuming $q = C_q L^\alpha$, we only need to show that if $\alpha \neq \alpha^* = \frac{1}{3}$, or $C_q \neq C_q^*$, it holds $\max_k \rho_C(k, L, q) > \max_k \rho_C(k, L, q^*)$ for h small enough. When $\alpha < \alpha^*$, an expansion for h small gives

$$\rho_C(\bar{k}, L, q) = 1 - \frac{4}{\sqrt{\varepsilon C_q}} C_1^{\frac{1-\alpha}{2}} h^{\frac{1-\alpha}{2}} + O(h^{1-\alpha}).$$

Since $\frac{1-\alpha}{2} > \frac{1}{3}$ for $\alpha < \frac{1}{3}$, we conclude that for sufficiently small h it holds

$$\rho_C(\bar{k}, L, q) > \rho_C(\bar{k}, L, q^*) = 1 - O(h^{\frac{1}{3}}).$$

When $\alpha > \alpha^*$, we have for h small

$$\rho_C(k_{min}, L, q) = 1 - \varsigma_{min} C_q C_1^\alpha h^\alpha + O(h^{\min\{2\alpha, 1\}}),$$

which is definitely greater than $\rho_C(k_{min}, L, q^*)$ for sufficiently small h . We now consider the case $\alpha = \alpha^*$ but $C_q \neq C_q^*$. By the asymptotic expansions above we find that $\rho_C(k_{min}, L, q) > \rho_C(k_{min}, L, q^*)$ if $C_q > C_q^*$ and $\rho_C(\bar{k}, L, q) > \rho_C(\bar{k}, L, q^*)$ if $C_q < C_q^*$.

Finally, to show the convergence factor estimate, we only expand $\rho_C(k_{min}, L, q^*)$ with q^* defined in (29) for h small. \square

C: Proof of Theorem 6

Proof. The convergence factor simplifies to

$$\rho_C(k, 0, q) = \frac{a(k)^2 + (b(k) - qk)^2}{a(k)^2 + (b(k) + qk)^2},$$

and the free parameter q can then be determined by solving the min-max problem

$$\min_{q>0} \max_{k \in \mathbb{K}} \rho_C(k, 0, q).$$

If we make ansatz $q^* = c_q^* k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}}$, and assume k_{max} is large enough, then we have

$$\rho_C(k_{min}, 0, q^*) = 1 - \varsigma_{min} c_q^* k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}} + O(k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{2}}), \quad (51a)$$

$$\rho_C(k_{max}, 0, q^*) = 1 - 2\sqrt{2}/(\sqrt{\varepsilon} c_q^*) k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}} + O(k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{2}}). \quad (51b)$$

where $\varsigma_{min} = 4k_{min}b_{min}/(a_{min}^2 + b_{min}^2)$. Matching the coefficients of the term $k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}}$ in (51a) and (51b), i.e., setting $\varsigma_{min} c_q^* = 2\sqrt{2}/(\sqrt{\varepsilon} c_q^*)$, one finds $c_q^* = 2^{\frac{3}{4}} \varepsilon^{-\frac{1}{4}} \varsigma_{min}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, which leads to (30).

We now need to show that $\rho_C(k, 0, q)$ attains its maximum asymptotically at either $k = k_{min}$ or $k = k_{max}$. Actually, this analysis is very similar to those for overlapping case, we thus omit the detail.

We are in the position to show that q^* given by (30) solves the min-max problem (25) with $L = 0$ asymptotically. Similar to the previous analysis, assuming that $q = c_q k_{max}^{-\alpha}$, we only need to show that if $\alpha \neq \alpha^* = \frac{1}{4}$ or $c_q \neq c_q^*$, it holds $\max_k \rho_C(k, 0, q) > \max_k \rho_C(k, 0, q^*)$ for sufficiently large k_{max} . When $\alpha < \alpha^*$, we have

$$\rho_C(k_{max}, 0, q) = 1 - 2\sqrt{2}/(\sqrt{\varepsilon} c_q) k_{max}^{-\frac{1-2\alpha}{2}} + O(k_{max}^{-2\alpha}).$$

Since $\frac{1-2\alpha}{2} > \frac{1}{4}$ for $\alpha < \frac{1}{4} = \alpha^*$, we claim that for sufficiently large k_{max} it holds

$$\rho_C(k_{max}, 0, q) > \rho_C(k_{max}, 0, q^*) = 1 - O(k_{max}^{-\frac{1}{4}}).$$

When $\alpha > \alpha^*$, we consider the convergence factor at k_{min} ,

$$\rho_C(k_{min}, 0, q) = 1 - \varsigma_{min} c_q k_{max}^{-\alpha} + O(k_{max}^{-2\alpha}),$$

which is bigger than $\rho_C(k_{min}, 0, q^*)$ if k_{max} is large enough. We then consider the case $\alpha = \alpha^*$ but $c_q \neq c_q^*$. By the asymptotic expansions above we find that if $c_q > c_q^*$, we have $\rho_C(k_{min}, 0, q) > \rho_C(k_{min}, 0, q^*)$, and if $c_q < c_q^*$ we obtain $\rho_C(k_{max}, 0, q) > \rho_C(k_{max}, 0, q^*)$, which concludes the proof of asymptotic optimality.

To show the convergence factor estimate, we only insert c_q^* and α^* into (51a). \square

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